

D2.1

User and Ecosystem Requirements and Methodology USAAR

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User and Ecosystem Requirements and Methodology

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Abstract

This document outlines the user and ecosystem requirements identified from related research projects and literature research. Some key aspects of the ecosystem user requirements were collected through a stakeholder survey. The ethical and medical considerations for the ecosystem described and the key legal requirements, form the framework for a future implementation plan. An outline of technical and artificial intelligence considerations is listed for a state-of-the-art ecosystem foundation. High level insights reflect the political situation.

Keywords

User Requirements, Ethics, Regulatory Framework, Technical Considerations, Methodology

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Nature of the deliverable

R*

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to EU4CHILD project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIMDD	Active Implantable Medical Devices
CTIS	Clinical Trials Information System
DAA	Data Access Agreement
DNN	Deep Neural Networks
DPA	Data Processor Agreement
EHR	Electronic Health Records
EP	Ependymoma
ERN	European Reference Network
ES	Eligibility Screening
FL	Federated Learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GWAS/TWAS	Genome-Wide / Transcriptome-Wide Association Studies
IE	Information Extraction
IVDMD	In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices
IVDR	In Vitro Diagnostics Regulation
MB	Medulloblastoma
MDD	Medical Devices
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
ML	Machine Learning
MRE	Model Runtime Environment
NCI	National Cancer Institute
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
QoL	Quality of Life
RI	Research Infrastructure
RIA	Research & Innovation Action
SoA	State of the Art
VPH	Virtual Physiological Human
WES	Whole Exome Sequencing
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing

1 Executive Summary

As part of Task 2 for the EU4CHILD project, this document outlines the general requirements and methodology definition for the Childhood Cancer Ecosystem including user-requirements from identified stakeholders. Initial user requirements are identified through literature research and a questionnaire. Additionally, legal and ethical requirements for the ecosystem are discussed, technical and AI considerations described and high-level insights are presented. This deliverable will be followed by D2.2 – Childhood Cancer Implementation State-of-the-Art Report (M09) and then D4.3 – Roadmap for the successful implementation of the Ecosystem (M18). This document is part of the milestone M2.1 requirements, which will be reached by M04. The final milestone of this task will be MS2.2, which will be reached by M09.

As requirements and methodologies are evolving over time and answers to the questionnaire (chapter 3.4 of this document) are still incoming, the results from the questionnaire will be continuously updated during the lifetime of the project.

2 Introduction

EU4CHILD will design and propose a European interoperable distributed marketplace framework for Paediatric Cancer (Neuroblastoma and Nephroblastoma) artificial intelligence (AI) research and knowledge exchange capable of data collection from Electronic Health Records (EHR), Medical Records, datasets and crowdsourced assets and data labelling, aligned to stakeholders' needs while respecting their privacy at the same time. This will pave the way towards consolidating in the future, a point of access for integrated healthcare and research data platforms that collate clinical data, including, clinical and clerical information, relevant diagnostic tests (pathology, “omics” data, radiological imaging), treatment interventions and clinical outcomes for childhood cancers. This deliverable D2.1 User and Ecosystem Requirements and Methodology belongs to the Pilot project: Developing Artificial Intelligence for diagnosis and treatment of paediatric cancer EU4CHILD.

The objectives of the project are the following:

- To create a complete multi-perspective (ethical, privacy, governance, medical-based, IT, AI specialists, infrastructure and industry) and State-of-the-Art (SoA) implementation plan for a medical decision support system.
- To develop a roadmap exploring the possibilities to implement the EU4CHILD platform under the identified requirements of the stakeholders while providing guidelines about the mechanisms and tools for engaging all stakeholders (e.g., fostering the explainability of AI for detection based on evidence) in a unified and holistic ecosystem construction.
- To build a framework that will incorporate all initiatives, datasets and solutions across Europe, as a reference to access the information, enabling integration through practical and research collaboration opportunities across sectors, disciplines, and geographical boundaries.
- To foster community building and engagement among all European actors, creating a multi-stakeholder network that will develop working streams with digital initiatives designed to support diverse paediatric cancer pathways' support.

2.1 Structure of the Document

The structure of this document is as follows:

- Section **Error! Reference source not found.** includes the end user requirements and collected stakeholder information.
- Section 0 presents the ethical and medical considerations required.
- Section 5 describes the technical consideration for the EU4CHILD ecosystem.
- Section 6 includes the high-level insight for such an interdisciplinary ecosystem.
- Section 7 presents conclusions and further actions to be taken.
- The Appendix contains the used questionnaire.

3 Methodology

To find user-requirements from the end user perspectives of an ecosystem that is intended to provide medical advice through AI, the EU4CHILD project addresses this in a unique methodology derived from the complementary disciplines present in the consortium.

This document will present results from literature research and the evaluation of an initial questionnaire. As part of this project, Deliverable D4.1 investigates the end user perspectives from a qualitative side incorporating the needs of children and adolescents living with cancer and their caregivers, patient and parent organizations and society as a whole. Deliverable D2.2 of EU4CHILD will describe the initiatives for cancer data sharing and large-scale repositories in Europe and their State-of-the-Art approaches.

3.1 Stakeholder

The stakeholder identified for the EU4CHILD ecosystem are wide spread throughout the field of medicine, science and policy making and ultimately affect society as a whole to bring improvements to the diagnosis and treatment of children and adolescents with rare diseases.

A list of stakeholders for the EU4CHILD ecosystem:

- Children and adolescents with cancer and their caregivers
- Clinicians and medical professionals
- Health care providers
- IT professionals and data scientists
- Patient and parent organizations
- Scientists, such as basic scientists in the field of biology, genetics and pharmacy to only name a few.
- Policy makers and decision makers
- AI Service Providers
- Society as a whole
- Data Protection Officers and Ethics Committees

Figure 1 show the connections between stakeholders with some needs and requirements that could be anticipated between stakeholders. The EU4CHILD consortium has initial topics identified from the partners' own backgrounds. These are the needs of Clinicians to have more time for patient treatment by reduced time in diagnostics though e.g., prediction models, which could be provided by IT Professionals. In turn IT professionals might expect more detailed data from Basic Scientists which were produced with improved experiment planning, as asked by Medical. Children living with cancer and their parents might expect improved healthcare that could be provided by clinicians though the use of AI technologies. Additionally, patients, their families, patient and parent organizations and the Society might approach Policy Makers to reduce hurdles of data collection and sharing to speed up the development of new treatments supported by AI.

Figure 1. EU4CHILD Stakeholder diagram with needs and requirements to each other.

In this chapter, stakeholder requirements are collected by literature research and through a questionnaire. In case stakeholders or use cases could not be covered through these means, the roadmap to fill the gaps will be laid out.

3.2 Literature Research

The literature research was performed to identify user requirements of the EU4CHILD stakeholder groups. The goal was to identify publications or projects describing possible EU4CHILD user requirements, which they identified for further development or research. Furthermore, the identified user requirements will be used for the EU4CHILD ecosystem implementation plan. For this, three sources different sources were used. The first source is CORDIS which was searched for similar or matching projects, the second source for literature is a PubMed search and third are other sources.

1.) The following projects were found through CORDIS on the 4th of June 2021. MyPal is an ongoing EU funded project, where USAAR is a partner:

The EU-STANDS4PM project is an EU Horizon 2020 project, which works towards standardization guidelines for *in silico* approaches in personalized medicine. To this end, EU-Stands4PM released a new harmonised Data Access Agreement for Controlled Access Data,

which allows to make sharing data throughout research projects simpler for the administrative side. Additionally, E-Stands4PM plans to release an ISO specification for data integration, data harmonization and in silico model validation. Results from these projects will be used for the implementation plan of the EU4CHILD ecosystem to strengthen the role of standardization in medicine overall and will expand on standards in this project. This relies mainly on the fact that this project involves children. There are specific ethical and legal regulations to be followed related to minors.

EU-STANDS4PM provides a forum[3] to assess strategies for health data integration and computer modelling (in silico). Their approach is to combine the formal standards with the community standards, that “usually reflect the results of a specific user group and are created by individual enterprises or communities” ([3] section 3.2). Some of the most usual challenges regarding standardization include a long approval process for a standard, the fact that the most supported standards might be selected over the best standards and also the acceptance of the community that is going to use it. The future of personalized medicine is dependent on an exchange of data from different sources. This consortium has developed a European Standardization Framework for Data Integration and Data-Driven *in silico* models for personalized medicine. The framework will set the basis for the EU4CHILD AI Framework’s own Data Access Agreement (DAA) [4] and relates to the EU4CHILD objectives 3 and 4.

CORBEL is a H2020-EU funded project¹ which focuses on the social and economic challenges of ageing populations and chronic disease. The CORBEL consortium aims to translate biomedical discoveries to new, innovative and cost-effective treatments. User requirements results from their work for the stakeholders Clinicians and Basics Scientists (biology) are available through the CORBEL Final Stakeholder Meeting Deliverable D2.4². The needs for harmonizing user access to in life sciences infrastructures are covered, which could be decision support systems such as the proposed EU4CHILD ecosystem. They presented work by scientists from the biological and medical user communities which illustrated how concerted access to multiple research infrastructures (RIs) advanced their projects, thus demonstrating the benefit of CORBEL for European life science research. This applies to the projects objectives 3 and 4 to build a framework for integrating existing databases and fostering community building.

The work *Sharing and reuse of individual participant data from clinical trials: principles and recommendations* by Ohmann et al.[18] describes 10 principles and 50 recommendations, representing the fundamental requirements of any framework used for the sharing of clinical trials data. These principles and recommendations were found by a group of experts through a consensus process as part of the CORBEL project. Although this publication does not cover AI or machine learning (ML) in particular, a focus of the presented principles is machine readability

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/654248> last visited 2021/08/18

² <https://zenodo.org/record/3744803> last visited 2021/08/18

and machine discoverability of the data, which are requirements that are aligned to the needs of the EU4CHILD stakeholders. The described principles will be used in relation of objection 1 and 2 as a design fundament for technical decisions.

MyPal³ is funded from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. Their research topic is fostering palliative care of adults and children with cancer through advanced patient reported outcome (PRO) systems. As part of their work, they identified user needs for palliative care for children and adults⁴, which can be used for the EU4CHILD ecosystem user requirements, since the MyPal project also uses a digital form of patient interaction through smartphones. Stakeholders from the EU4CHILD project for which MyPal provides valuable information are patients (children, teenager, young adults) and their parents. The use of PROs as additional data source will be included in the EU4CHILD data framework in relation to objective 1 and 2.

2.) The following papers were found through PubMed on the 7th of June 2021 with the search string “artificial intelligence methodology child* cancer review”. The used search string did produce over 50 results which were manually reviewed, Figure 2 depicts the selection process. The following 8 publications remained:

The work by Lehmann et al. [1] is not targeted to childhood cancer in particular, but rather to oncology as a field. Stakeholders in this publication are data scientists and medical professionals. The paper shows the need to transfer oncology models for survival, detection and classification into clinical practice, which is currently lacking. Lehmann et al. also points out the use of patient reported outcome (PRO) as an additional input for prediction models. PROs are used to assess the patient’s quality of life (QoL) and could be used to identify changes in the patient’s health status. This relates to the EU4CHILD objectives 1 to expand AI capabilities and objective 2 to expand the projects databases with new data sources.

The publication *Artificial intelligence in paediatric radiology: Future opportunities* by Davendralingam et al. [5] suggests how AI can be used in paediatric radiology but not only in oncology by optimizing patient booking and this waiting time reduction. User requirements for the medical professionals and the administrative side in clinics for patient management can be drawn from this paper. This relates to objective 1 for the adoption of SoA patient management.

The paper *Pharmacogenomic and Pharmacotranscriptomic Profiling of Childhood Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia: Paving the Way to Personalized Treatment* by Pavlovic et al.[6] contains several requirements for data scientists on treatment related data in medicine. These

³ <https://mypal-project.eu/> last visited 2021/08/18

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825872/results> last visited 2021/08/18

data are for example the preferred usage of microarray technology vs targeted DNA sequencing, whole exome sequencing (WES), whole genome sequencing (WGS) or RNA sequencing. The paper points out that most genome-wide / transcriptome-wide association studies (GWAS/TWAS) have provided contradictory results. Reasons for that identified by the authors could be not uniformly selected patient cohorts selected for the GWAS/TWAS and lack of knowledge of the complete biomarker profile at the beginning of the disease could lead to false conclusions at the end. Furthermore, the paper provides suggestions on how to select target genes and form patient cohorts to avoid most found reasons for possible contradictory results. Suggestions are that phenotype endpoints should be precisely defined and the design of the experiments and the genotype/transcriptome calling process must be checked very accurately, since those are a common source of inconsistencies in GWAS/TWAS. User requirements for data scientists can be drawn from this work to precisely select patient cohorts and carefully design experiments and data interpretation. This relates to objective 2 to implement a reliable source of evidence to be analysed through AI technologies.

The work *Artificial Intelligence–Assisted Prediction of Late-Onset Cardiomyopathy Among Childhood Cancer Survivors* by Güntürkün et al.[7] shows that ECG need to be pre-processed in the clinic improve that data content for their model. As the authors state: “the features identified in our models are not immediately interpretable and bear little relationship to classical ECG characteristics such as p-waves, QRS complexes, and t-waves typically used for diagnosis of chamber dysfunction. Clinical use of our model will require its execution on the digital data underlying standard 12-lead ECGs—a computationally simple task—to generate a risk score for future cardiomyopathy”. This shows the collection of only certain data features from one experiment are not sufficient and that the EU4CHILD ecosystem should motivate medical experts to share all available data. Additionally, the paper motivates further creation of patient cohort in relation to objectives 3 and 4, since only on large cohort of childhood cancer survivors exists.

The paper *Deep Learning for Pediatric Posterior Fossa Tumor Detection and Classification: A Multi-Institutional Study* by Quon et al.[8] shows the need for cooperation between different clinical sites and contracts for data sharing to increase data availability. The work contains information for the stakeholders' medical professionals and data scientists to motivate user requirements for standardizes clinical data collection. Additionally, the authors point out that that segmentation and classification models can augment the radiologist's performance. A citation from the paper: “As the discussion on artificial intelligence in medicine continues to evolve, the radiology community has suggested a potential role for artificial intelligence in augmenting care by bridging knowledge gaps among clinical experts. In this context, we propose that our model could serve to augment the radiologist's performance, particularly among those less experienced in paediatric neuro-oncology”. Furthermore, the authors noted that the developed model outperformed clinical experts only for certain tumour pathology and certain scan techniques: “Compared with the average performance of human experts, the model more accurately predicted all tumour types except for

ependymoma (EP). This outcome might be attributed to the smaller proportion of EP in the training set. It is also possible that learned features for EP overlapped with those of medulloblastoma (MB) (...).” The work relates to the EU4CHILD objectives 1 and 2 for technical advances and to objectives 3 and 4 for fostering data exchange between clinics.

The paper *Automatic Machine Learning to Differentiate Pediatric Posterior Fossa Tumors on Routine MR Imaging* by Zhou et al. [9] motives to collect a variety of clinical data and not just e.g., imaging data. Also, the work shows the need for cooperation between different clinical sides. Both are stakeholder requirements of the group's medical professionals and data scientists. The authors of the paper point out the importance of tumor classification through histopathology, since imaging of the tumour is not sufficient: “Despite the robustness of these results, the classification scheme in the present study does not obviate tumor diagnosis by histopathology, the criterion standard. Histopathology is needed for a truly confirmatory diagnosis, offers the opportunity to profile non tumour cells in the tumour mass that play an important role in the pathogenesis of these malignancies and classifies tumours into molecular subgroups that are not appreciated by imaging. In an era of personalized medicine and therapeutic approaches like immunotherapy, these factors are especially important.”. However, the authors suggest to improve upon current imaging standards and pushing towards the adoption of advanced imaging modalities such as MR spectroscopy and MR perfusion, which may improve the model performance. This is an important point for the EU4CHILD ecosystem, where the adoption of new technologies could be motivated through data collection requirements in relation to objectives 1 and 2.

The paper *Distinguishing between pediatric brain tumour types using multi-parametric magnetic resonance imaging and machine learning: A multi-site study* by Grist et al. [10] shows the need for multi-site studies for rear tumours to increase participant numbers in relation to the EU4CHILD objectives 3 and 4. This recurring theme shows how crucial collaboration between different clinical sites can improve data availability and quality. Also, the authors recommend the usage of new imaging technologies: “Challenges are faced in the acquisition of DSC data, particularly the injection of gadolinium in a highly regulated manner in children and the use of arterial spin labelling. These may present an alternative option for utilizing perfusion imaging in the future.”.

The publication *Increasing the efficiency of trial-patient matching: automated clinical trial eligibility Pre-screening for pediatric oncology patients* by Ni et al.[11] does not employ machine learning, but rather natural language processing (NLP) and information extraction (IE) technologies to find suitable patients for oncology trials. However, the importance of complete electronic health records (EHR) can be drawn from this work for the stakeholders, specifically data scientists and medical professionals. The authors suggest that automated eligibility screening (ES) of HER could reduce time for patient enrolment: “In a retrospective evaluation of real-world data, the algorithm achieved 85% workload reduction in trial-centered patient cohort identification and more than 90% in patient-centered trial recommendation, while keeping the precision at a manageable level

(12.6% and 35.7% respectively)". The prospective evaluation of this finding can be managed through the EU4CHILD ecosystem.

Figure 2. Selection process of the manual review for the found publication on PubMed.

3.) The following work was retrieved through other sources:

Research2Guidance⁵ published a report on their survey conducted for the first year of the COVID-19-pandemic covering how the digital health industry has changes [2]. The work covers stakeholders medical professionals, healthcare providers and AI/IT service providers. The report shows that 42% of the replies to the survey are from digital health companies. Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, digital healthcare solutions showed increases acceptance from users and payors by e.g., telehealth and remote patient management systems, digital vaccination management software and digital appointment scheduling. This is a considerable uptake on digital health care systems compared to their adoption before the pandemic.

The European Reference Network (ERN) performed a user consultation on a Mobile App for ERNs on behalf of the European Commission. A total of 441 respondents participated in the survey, mainly clinicians. The user consultation survey results are not publicly available at the

⁵ <https://research2guidance.com/>

time of writing the document, results presented here are preliminary. Most answers were positive regarding the development of an ERN Mobile App. The respondents expressed their wishes for a simple to use invite system to the App, a medical experts list and more flexibility in terms of user roles and access. Most respondents noted that a Mobile App represents a time gain. Concerns were raised towards medical imaging and visibility on mobile device. These findings can be used to design the software as mobile app or web platform which gives access to the EU4CHILD ecosystem and thus the AI and ML applications.

The EU FP7 funded project CONTRACT conducted a survey for their deliverables D2.2 among clinicians, chairpersons of research projects, basics researchers, computer scientists, legal experts and others across Europe. A part of this questionnaire was regarding the use of informed consent in a clinical context. Although the questionnaire was conducted in 2011, before the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the results are still relevant. The questionnaire results were answered by up to 120 participants. 45 respondents noted that that signed an informed consent form, 41 form themselves. Only 19 received a copy of the consent form, which is less than half. The respondents who signed such a form felt mostly comfortable with the process but felt only partially informed about the medical and legal implications. The results offer more details, but show overall that the process of informed consent can be improved for all involved stakeholders. This topic is not directly related to the application of AI for childhood cancer, but becomes even more a necessity for data driven application as AI.

3.3 Beyond Literature Research

Stakeholders, for which no requirements to the EU4CHILD ecosystem were found through literature research, requirements will be collected through a questionnaire. These stakeholders are patients and their families, policy makers, health care service providers and society as a whole.

The collected information presents state-of-the-art requirements by AI professionals and medical professionals for robust data. However, user stakeholder groups of this project, such as children and adolescents and their caregivers, patient and parent organisations and others, could be covered by literature research alone. Some of these stakeholder groups are covered in Deliverable D4.1 – Impact Master Plan – of this project, which will be released besides this document. The section 3.4 “Target Groups” of D4.1 described stakeholder needs for this project from qualitative research.

To further reach stakeholders of this project, the use of in-depth interviews and focus-panels will be evaluated, depending what methods work best to connect with the stakeholders.

Topics for further stakeholder interviews or questionnaires can be:

- Acceptance of decision support (patients, families, healthcare professionals)

- Parents', of children with cancer, fear for the life of their child, which might motivate them "to do anything". This raises the question if informed consent was given freely for e.g., the collection of data and biomaterial or the participation in clinical trials.
- Data protection hurdles experienced in the approval process of clinical studies, the approval process of in silico model for medical applications and in day-to-day clinical practice.
- How is rehabilitation with telemedicine perceived?
- Others that will be identified through further research.

As part of the implementation plan, we suggest a validation of the hypothesized requirements once an implementation of the EU4CHILD ecosystem exists. For this, EU project OpenReq⁶ can be employed, which allows to collect and visualize user requirements of software systems. The initial hypothesis can be tested through OpenReq and refined, which allows to iteratively improve the user requirements and thus the ecosystem.

3.4 Questionnaire

The questionnaire was designed to capture initial suggestions to key problems from all stakeholders. Key problems, identified by the EU4CHILD consortium for the ecosystem, are data sharing, the knowledge of AI and the view of all stakeholders on data confidentiality in the clinical setting.

To evaluate the result of the completed questionnaire, we propose three research questions:

1. We want to show that there are differences in answers between the different stakeholders.
2. This will lead to the question if we need separate actions for the different stakeholders depending on their differences in answers?
3. We will be able to draw actions from the free text answers of our fictional scenario.

The questionnaire was made publicly available online on 2021/07/29 through the project's website, posts in social media like Twitter and LinkedIn and was sent to collaborators, friends and family of EU4CHILD consortium members. Survey results were retrieved on 2021/09/08.

3.4.1 Completed Questionnaire - Results

The questionnaire was open for a 6-week period and 41 respondents answered the 16 questions of the questionnaire. The number of respondents is relatively low considering the wide range of stakeholders. A possible reason could be the summer vacation time or the limited time of 4 months that were available to prepare and distribute the questionnaire. Three technical difficulties were reported where respondents noted a not loading webpage, an encountered network error and an

⁶ <https://openreq.eu/> last visited 2021/07/30

error in the questionnaire navigation that prevented them to proceed. For some questions the respondents were able to answer in a free text field. The answers were translated to English for the analysis by the authors of this document with the help of DeepL⁷.

The respondents are equally distributed between the male and female sex and throughout all ages (**Figure 3**). Most respondents identified their domain as “Citizens” closely followed by “Researcher” and “Healthcare” (**Figure 4**). From the domain of healthcare most respondents are medical professionals and most respondents from the Research domain are from the field of Data Science.

Figure 3. Age and gender distribution of the questionnaire respondents.

⁷ <https://www.deepl.com/translator>

Figure 4. The domain from which the respondents answered the questionnaire with a detailed view on the Research and Healthcare domain.

The respondents were asked about their knowledge of AI in their respective area of expertise (**Figure 5**). No one answered “very good knowledge of AI”, most respondents answered “normal” to “somewhat poor” Knowledge in AI. Almost all respondents think that AI will be useful in medicine for diagnostics and treatment (**Figure 6**).

Further questions towards the respondent’s knowledge in the field of AI were for AI reporting guidelines in medicine, for which only two respondents indicated knowledge. In contrast to this close to 50 percent of the respondents reported knowledge about AI tools and protocols for data sharing (**Figure 7**).

Figure 5. AI Knowledge of the respondents in their respective fields.

Figure 6. Respondents perceived usefulness of AI in medicine.

Figure 7. Knowledge of the respondents of AI reporting guidelines in medicine and AT tools and protocols for sharing of medical data.

The questionnaire continues towards the respondents view of the confidentiality of medical data in everyday clinical practice and in research projects. Furthermore, respondents who are parents (25 respondents) were asked the same questions for their children’s data (**Figure 8** and **Figure 9**). As the figures show are the participant fairly confident that their data and their children’s data are handled confidentially. Only two respondents were “little confident” to “not confident” for the general use of data and no respondents selected these options in the questions aim towards the children’s data.

Figure 8. Confidence of the respondents in the confidentiality of medical data in everyday practice (left) and in research projects (right).

Figure 9. Confidence of the respondents in the confidentiality of the children's medical data in everyday practice (left) and in research projects (right).

The next topic in the questionnaire is the respondents view of on regulations towards the protection of health data and whether they believe privacy regulations are delaying research results (**Figure 10**). Respondents abstained from answering these to questions in 37% and 26% cases respectively. If the question “Do you think that the health data protection regulations that exist today are adequate?” was answered with “No”, the respondents were asked to describe their answer in a free text field. They were also asked to describe their answer if they answered “Yes” to the questions “Do you believe that privacy regulations are delaying research results?”.

In 4 instances were individual asked for the first questions towards adequate data protection regulations recorded. One participant noted towards stronger regulations, it could be possible to identify individuals. Two respondents commented towards a less strong regulation that reuse and sharing of the data is too difficult and practicability of the regulations is not given. One comment is too vague “too many interfaces”, since the statement could be interpreted either way.

In 25 instances individuals found the privacy regulations delaying research results and provided comments on the topic. The general notion from all respondents is that the current data protection regulations increase bureaucracy and documentation obligations further for patients donating their data and also for parties receiving the data. The difficulties for data re-use and data sharing were mentioned several times and that requirements for anonymization of data often conflicts with needed data quality and integration. Only one participant provided a remark that has a positive aspect towards data protection: “Although it is delayed, but no research without rules”.

The respondents did not only object to the current data protection hurdles for research, they provided feedback on what can be improved in their point of view:

- “Informed consent should ensure the use of data in a more general way by preserving the privacy of the data but allowing their use in future studies not yet defined at the time of subscription. Citizens should be allowed to be able to trust the ethics committees of research centers more by making them aware of their existence.”
- “International [...] applicable standards (including detailed procedures for taking protective measures and sample documents for implementing and demonstrating compliance with

these standards) for the protection of sensitive clinical data could help to make (the most diverse) data sets generally available and thus available for research.”

- Several comments noted that new data protection regulations should take the medical and humanitarian progress into account to adopt faster to new technologies. New regulations should be oriented towards supporting and improving current processes of scientific data collection and usage in medicine instead of added new processes on top.

Figure 10. For these two questions the respondents were asked their view if the current health data protection regulations are adequate (left) and if they believe that privacy regulations are delaying research results.

The questionnaire proposed next a fictional scenario: (see **Figure 11**)

Let us imagine that you are living the following situation:

You are the parent of a child who has been diagnosed with an inoperable brain tumor (brainstem tumor). You have been informed by the treating paediatric oncologists that the prognosis of the disease is very poor and that no cure is possible with conventional therapies. Since the treatment and prognosis of this disease has not changed fundamentally in the last 30 years, you will be introduced to a research project in which you can help to develop an AI system that could improve the treatment of brain stem tumors.

For this, all possible data of your child from symptoms to laboratory values, pathological data, genetic data of the tumor and imaging data (CT, MRI) are needed to create a model of the tumor in order to find individual and new therapy options. These data must first be collected from many children with the same disease in order to process and evaluate them in the research project. The hope is that this may lead to a new treatment option for your child.

Figure 11. First scenario description of the questionnaire.

The respondents were asked to provide their child’s data in pseudonymized form for the research in the described context. Following this question, they were asked if they would still provide their

child's data if the prognosis was significantly better compared to the described scenario (**Figure 12**). In the first scenario, all respondents agreed to share their child's data, in the second scenario all but one was willing to share the data with one abstention. In case respondents would not be willing to share the data they would have been able to comment on their decision. Since there was no refusal to share the data, no comments were collected.

Figure 12. Respondents were put in a fictional scenario and asked to share their child's data under the described circumstances.

Following up on the fictional scenario, the respondents were also asked “Would you have a tissue sample taken from your child for molecular genetic analysis of the tumour and provide this data for research purposes? You have been informed that the result of the analysis may be of no significance for your child, but will in principle provide new insights into this tumour.”. The respondents were willing to share tissue data in 34 cases, 4 respondents have abstained and 3 respondents were not willing to share tissue data. From the respondents who were unwilling to share tissue data comments were provided. In all three cases, respondents wanted to spare their child from a procedure unless absolutely necessary.

Figure 13. Respondents were asked if they were willing to share tissue samples from their child.

The second fictional scenario is as follows: (see **Figure 14**).

Now, let's imagine another situation:

A childhood cancer research project was successful. An AI system for the treatment of brainstem tumors was developed.

Initial research results indicate that the use of the AI based system has a better prognosis than conventional treatment methods. However, the system has yet to be validated, as the actual benefit needs to be further assessed.

Figure 14. Second scenario description of the questionnaire.

Respondents were asked under what conditions they would participate with their child in the described study (**Figure 15**). Most of the respondents (17) were willing to join to support the goal of the AI study by principle. Ten Respondents would join the AI study because their child's prognosis is poor. 5 Respondents would like to understand the system before they would join the AI study and 8 respondents demanded additionally clear benefits for their child. One participant had other conditions, which were provided through a free text field: "I need to know the IT system, and the people that will be working on this. If I am to risk my child's data, I would prefer to make sure they are professionals."

Figure 15. Respondents were asked for the reason they would need to participate with their child in an AI supported study.

The final question asked for general comments on the questionnaire or the topic. One comment noted that multiple answers to the questions about what conditions respondents have to join the AI study apply. Another comment pointed out the need to increase economic and human resources in for the field of medical research to achieve a better quality of life. The last comment described the thoughts of the participant from several viewpoints: (see Figure 16)

- From a parent's point of view:
 - How well can it be explained to me what the difference is between human and AI decision in further treatment?
 - To what extent is the AI decision binding on the treating physician and how many points in the treatment are covered by AI? Is it only genetic and imaging analysis or does this affect the whole treatment plan?
- From a scientist's point of view:
 - Tissue samples are taken and used for this type of tumor. In the consent form, are these samples also released for other models to study a specific genetic mutation found in different types of cancer (lung, kidney, heart, brain, etc.)? This should be at least another consent point.
 - Since AI systems are not likely to be flexible enough for a complete treatment plan for a very long time: How will it be handled if the AI is unaware of certain incidents or does not have them in its assessment routine?
 - How quickly is an AI outdated because new knowledge has a better prognosis? This also raises the question of how much validation of AI systems cause delays in patient care.
- Long-term funding / data protection / long-term application:
 - Who is liable for failures?
 - Who is the operator of a "successful" AI?
 - How often are there new versions?
 - What are the costs?
 - Training and help desk?
 - Technical availability centralized or on-site installations necessary due to data protection?
 - How to keep systems current with new data after research aspect ends?
 - Long-term observations?

Figure 16. Informative free text answer from the final remarks of the questionnaire.

3.4.2 Analysis of Findings

Even though the number of respondents is relatively low, the response from the stakeholders *Clinicians and medical professionals, IT professionals and data scientists and Society as a whole* can be used to answer the proposed research questions and infer further actions for those stakeholders. The findings are grouped together by the research question below.

3.4.2.1 Question 1: We want to show that there are differences in answers between the different stakeholders.

- Finding 1: *Knowledge on AI*
 - **Figure 5** shows the perceived knowledge of the respondents of AI in their respective field. The results show that the three presented stakeholders have different levels of knowledge in the field of AI. Research reports a “good” to “normal” knowledge followed by Citizens and Healthcare participants. Interestingly did no one report a “very good” knowledge in AI although computer scientists are part of the Research group. The second finding is that Citizens report a relative high level of AI, slightly higher than the Research group.
- Finding 2: *Data Confidentiality in Clinical Settings*
 - **Figure 8** show the perceived confidence of three stakeholder groups in data confidentiality for the use case of medical practice and research projects. The results show the respondents from the research group perceive a higher confidentiality of medical data in research projects compared to medical practice. In general, is the data confidentiality of the Healthcare group lower compared to the groups Research and Citizen.
- Finding 3: *Adequacy of Health Data Regulations and Delay on Research Results by Privacy Regulations*
 - **Figure 17** shows the respondents view on the adequacy of health data protection regulations and if privacy regulations delay research. This result shows that most respondents found the health data regulations adequate and found that privacy regulations delay research. More respondents from the group Citizens abstained from these two questions than found the regulation adequate.

Figure 17. Respondents view on the adequacy of health data regulation and if privacy regulations delay research separated by stakeholder domains.

3.4.2.2 **Question 2:** This will lead to the question if we need separate actions for the different stakeholders depending on their differences in answers?

- Action resulting from Finding 1:
 - Finding 1 shows that different stakeholders need to be addressed on different levels towards the field of AI with specialized information material and education campaigns. However, even stakeholders from a non-technical background such as Citizens indicated a good knowledge of AI. This leads to the necessity to understand their perceived knowledge of AI in greater detail to understand their meaning of the term.
- Action resulting from Finding 2:
 - Finding 2 shows the different perception of stake holder groups for the confidentiality of medical data in medical practice and research project. This needs to be explored in more detail to understand why respondents from the group of healthcare view medical data confidentiality lower compared to other stakeholders and why data confidentiality in research projects is perceived higher compared to medical practice in general.
- Action resulting from Finding 3:
 - Finding 3 shows that respondents from the group of Citizen abstained from answering questions towards data privacy regulations. Further research has to be done to evaluate the knowledge of data privacy regulations for each group of stakeholders through an individualized approach.

3.4.2.3 **Question 3:** We will be able to draw actions from the free text answers of our fictional scenario.

The free text answers show in all instances a common direction, allowing actions to be drawn from them. The following actions are ordered according to the appearance of the corresponding items in the questionnaire. The order of the actions does not reflect the importance or relevance of the individual action.

- **Action 1:** Policymakers at EU and state, regional or local level must be urged to implement regulations that lower the legal hurdles for the collection, long term use and sharing of medical data for medical research. Current EU regulations appear to add new data protection regulations on top of existing ones instead of adopting current regulations for new requirements by new technical advances in healthcare. The action is drawn from the free text input for the questions towards the adequacy of data protection regulations of health data and the questions whether privacy regulations are delaying research results
- **Action 2:** Medical studies conducted through the EU4CHILD ecosystem are expected to ask for the donation of tissue samples only if the risks for the patients are offset by the benefits, either for the patient directly or for society indirectly, and sufficient material for the patient and

parents is available that describes the risks and benefits in an easy-to-understand way. The action is drawn from the question whether to share the tissue samples of children for research.

- **Action 3:** Regulations for AI medical support decision systems have to be developed by policymakers. The liability questions of AI systems in medicine must be established in order to facilitate the development of such systems and their application in practice. This action is drawn from the general comments.

4 Ethical and Medical Considerations

This chapter outlines ethical and medical considerations for the EU4CHILD ecosystem implementation plan. Requirements from the medical point of view for the research, diagnosis and treatment of rare diseases in children are given. Ethical and legal challenges for AI systems in medicine and children as patients will be discussed.

4.1 Introduction

The foundation of AI technologies for health care relies on data sharing which is needed to train algorithms (References [7], [9] and [10]). In the application of deep learning, accuracy of algorithms increases almost in a linear fashion with the amount of available data. Although data sharing is a universal challenge for any research activities, AI and paediatric cancer represents a specific domain. Under the GDPR umbrella, anonymized data may be shared provided that there is a legitimate interest to use them. However, being paediatric cancers rare diseases, there is a potential for reidentification. Moreover, AI studies often rely on gathering and pooling data from different sources, including genetic data, allowing for potential reidentification. Indeed, ethical committees may require an informed consent even in case of anonymized data for AI purposes. In other cases, pseudonymized or clearly identifiable data may be needed for some research purposes, requiring an informed consent. An additional challenge is that children are not autonomous and informed consent should be given by their parents or legal custodians. Not only do research studies in which data sharing is required may aim at developing diagnostic tools, but there is an increasing interest in digital therapies for whom the active principle is a software possibly driven by AI instead of a chemical or a biological compound or a physical procedure. In all these cases, a tailored and understandable informed consent from patients and families is necessary, in accordance with the medical expertise of the EU4CHILD consortium.

Several concepts in the explanation of risks and benefits associated with AI may be difficult to explain resulting in the “black box” problem. Although AI systems are fed known input data and generate explicit output data, the logic behind an AI algorithm may be opaque. This makes it difficult to understand, and explain how, and the reason why an algorithm arrived at a specific result. As the European Commission considers transparency a fundamental requirement for AI systems in healthcare, lack of explainability may have important ethical and legal implications. Another issue may be the development of a biased AI algorithm when a training set for an AI algorithm excludes, for example, individuals from disadvantaged communities. Finally, being an AI based software, one may consider the risk of cyberattacks that, on one hand, may lead to privacy problems, and on the other hand may lead to deployment problems for AI applications. These background considerations suggest some specific needs in developing informed consent strategies for AI applications:

- Developing specific frameworks for informed consent in AI interventions that clearly address explainability of algorithms, potential bias and a risk/benefit analysis including evaluation guidelines and checklists
- Involving in the development of these strategies all stakeholders, from families to clinicians, to ethicists and data scientists and promoting research that aims to make these tools usable and understandable
- Developing the capacity and the skills of Ethical Committees in better understanding the details of AI interventions and performing a risk/benefit analysis to improve the review process of clinical studies involving AI interventions

The wide availability of electronic health records has fuelled the hope that clinical data sharing for research purposes was handy. A more pragmatic view has underlined how data regarding patients are not only fragmented, but often stored in silos. A typical health provider, then, may need not only to extract information from their EHR platforms, but also to connect with other existing applications, and often with other data sources like wearable devices, creating potential technological issues.

Data sharing is subject to the monitoring activities of data protection officers who have the role to guarantee that privacy during data sharing is preserved and that the potential of data breach is at minimum level. When data should be transferred to other entities, a contract defining data flows and responsibility should be prepared and signed by all parties. Unfortunately, the role of DPO remains often limited to a segment of the entire process leading to long procedures. In addition to, international regulations on data privacy, are often interpreted locally, creating divergencies between data providers.

An additional step in data sharing regards the scope for which data sharing is required and the ethical implication of the underlying case study. This evaluation should be always performed by an ethical committee in which, however, the experience and required skills for reviewing an AI project is often lacking.

Finally, one of the attempts to encourage research collaborations which is also instrumental to AI application, is providing open data. To access data from researchers and research institutions in a common repository is rare, however, few do allow their data to be available on “a reasonable request”. Some research projects and registries also tried to create common repositories with specific data access policies with mixed success. There is however a growing interest in opening the data from clinical trials to create accessible repositories. Furthermore, some drug companies already made data from some clinical trials available for other applications, hoping that “crowdsourcing” their analysis may create a benefit for them.

Considering these observations, the following needs may deserve to be addressed:

- Encouraging the creation and use of standards for data sharing not only for data formats but also for use at the macro level
- Continuing to support the creation of interoperability tools, including libraries of APIs focusing on paediatric oncology

- Supporting the discussion regarding the interpretation and the application of EU rules regarding data sharing and AI involving networks of European DPOs
- Exploring the potential advantages and limitations of blockchain technologies and synthetic data in developing AI applications

4.2 Related Projects

MyPal⁸ CHILD is a Horizon 2020 (H2020) Research & Innovation Action (RIA) project aiming to improve palliative care for children with cancer by the using a videogame as a mean to collect patient reported outcome (PRO) data. The PRO data could be used to adapt the caregiver's treatment to the patient, adapting the treatment to the personal needs of the patient. Ultimately, the PRO system should help identifying important deviations in the patient's state and quality of life (QoL). The ethical considerations by the MyPal project, available as Deliverable D1.1⁹, for the use of digital systems to be used by children will be considered for the EU4CHIL ecosystem implementation plan.

EU-STANDS4PM¹⁰ is a H2020 project aiming to develop relevant standards for in silico approaches in personalized medicine, implemented as pan-European expert forum and framework. The project published an in-depth ethical review of in silico modelling, which will be referenced by the EU4CHILD project as guidelines. The ethical review is available as Deliverable 3.1¹¹.

Share4Rare¹² is a H2020 project that aims to bring rare disease communities together. Their rare diseases library¹³ is a source for information on rare diseases and can be used for the EU4CHILD project as inspiration on how to educate patients and their family about these diseases. Additionally, the Share4Rare patient advocacy toolkit¹⁴ can be used as a blueprint to the EU4CHILD patient empowerment actions to give patients and survivors of cancer a voice.

The PRIMAGE project¹⁵ is also funded under the H2020 project of the European Union. The Project is devoted to developing methods of computational analysis of medical images applied to childhood cancer. They propose a cloud-based platform with decision support to assist with diagnosis, prognosis, therapy and treatment follow-up for malignant solid tumours.

⁸ <https://mypal-project.eu/>

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825872/results>

¹⁰ <https://www.eu-stands4pm.eu/home> last visited on 2021/07/27

¹¹ <https://www.eu-stands4pm.eu/publications> last visited on 2021/07/27

¹² <https://www.share4rare.org/> last visited on 2021/07/27

¹³ <https://www.share4rare.org/diseases/library> last visited on 2021/07/27

¹⁴ <https://www.share4rare.org/library/share4rare-toolkit-patient-advocacy/share4rare-toolkit-patient-advocacy> last visited on 2021/07/27

¹⁵ <https://www.primageproject.eu/> last visited 2021/08/26

4.3 Medical Consideration

The understanding of disease across multi-scale levels, molecular, cellular and physiological is challenging. This is especially true for cancer¹⁶ that may serve as a paradigm for other diseases. Obviously, it is difficult to tackle this challenge with pure biological means. Within Paediatric Oncology it is obvious that the progress over the last decades is mainly attributed to prospective, multicentre and randomized clinical trials. Despite high survival rates, further improvements are difficult to achieve with only clinical trials. For many cancer types it looks as there is a threshold for cure (**Figure 18**).

Figure 18. Survival probabilities by year of diagnosis Germany 1981-2016 in 66859 children with cancer.¹⁷

Therefore, multi-level data collection within clinico-genomic trials and interdisciplinary analysis by clinicians, molecular biologists and others involved in life science is mandatory to further improve the outcome not only of cancer patients but for all diseases, especially rare diseases. The more molecular data in individual patients are collected, the more a high variability of the same disease in different patients is recognized. As a result, diseases on an individual level are unique, in other words disease need to be considered rare or individualized.

It is essential to merge the research results of biomolecular findings, imaging studies, scientific

¹⁶ Deisboeck TS, et al. (2011). Multiscale Cancer Modeling. *Annu Rev Biomed Eng.* 13:127-55

¹⁷ Ertmann F et al. Childhood Cancer Register. Annual Report (2019); IMBEI, Mainz 2020

literature and clinical data from patients and to enable users to easily join, analyse and share even great amounts of data. The problem of sharing clinical data presents a major hurdle for the facilitation of research using that data. The data sources held by hospitals represent a major resource that is not adequately exploited, either by scientific researchers or clinicians. There is the need to gain access to these distributed data sources in a routine, transparent way, following appropriate anonymisation and security procedures, if patient specific medical simulations will be incorporated into clinical practice. While solutions exist to enable access to federate, distributed data sources, in many cases these are either not appropriate or acceptable to a hospital, or not generic enough to be used in anything other than the narrow scenarios for which they were developed.

There are also many problems related to the disparate nature of the data sources; data on the same clinical pathologies may be stored in different formats by different hospitals, with some data fields stored by some hospitals and not others. While some institutions may be in a position to impose some uniformity on the data imposed in its hospitals, where pan-European or international research is concerned, this is unlikely for many hospitals. The quality of data is another problem. In some clinical environments, certain data fields may not be stored routinely, leaving the available data incomplete.

Brunak S et al. wrote 2020 in their paper ‘Towards standardization guidelines for in silico approaches in personalized medicine’¹⁸ the following: “Despite the ever-progressing technological advances in producing data in health and clinical research, the generation of new knowledge for medical benefits through advanced analytics still lags behind its full potential. Reasons for this obstacle are the inherent heterogeneity of data sources and the lack of broadly accepted standards. Further hurdles are associated with legal and ethical issues surrounding the use of personal/patient data across disciplines and borders. Consequently, there is a need for broadly applicable standards compliant with legal and ethical regulations that allow interpretation of heterogeneous health data through *in silico* methodologies to advance personalized medicine”. For that purpose, EU-STANDS4PM “initiated an EU-wide mapping process to evaluate strategies for data integration and data-driven *in silico* modelling approaches to develop standards, recommendations and guidelines for personalized medicine.” Challenges for cross-domain data integration need further to be facilitated as well in AI models for rare diseases.

4.3.1 Medical Research of Rare Diseases

Medicine is undergoing a revolution that is transforming the nature of healthcare from *reactive to preventive* and *to a personalized predictive treatment*¹⁹. This transformation process has motivated the concept of the Virtual Physiological Human (VPH) that seeks to develop a scientific

¹⁸ Brunak S et al. [Journal of Integrative Bioinformatics](https://doi.org/10.1515/jib-2020-0006), 2020; <https://doi.org/10.1515/jib-2020-0006>

¹⁹ <http://www.cra.org/ccc/initiatives>

methodological and technological framework within which it is/will be possible to construct models of the human body as a single complex dynamical system. While research in VPH is going on resulting disease models simulators have not reached an acceptable level of maturity to be used in clinical routine. Especially in rare diseases this is a highly demanding endeavour. A sound multiscale and multidimensional modelling of the *natural phenomenon* of rare diseases is a *sine qua non* prerequisite for a clinically exploitable understanding of the disease as emphasized during the 1st Transatlantic Workshop on Multiscale Cancer Modelling, jointly funded by EC (ICT) and the National Cancer Institute in US (NCI) (Brussels 2008)²⁰.

Based on the latest advancements in the field, clinically driven complex multiscale cancer models can produce rather realistic spatial-temporal simulations of concrete clinical interventions such as radio-chemotherapy applied to individual patients. Clinical data processing procedures and computer technologies play an important role in this context. Following clinical adaptation and validation within the framework of clinico-genomic trials, models are expected to enhance individualized treatment optimization. The latter constitutes the long-term goal of the emergent scientific, technological and medical discipline of AI in medicine. Treatment optimization is to be achieved through experimentation on the computer. Moreover, provision of insight into rare diseases dynamics and optimization of clinical trial design and interpretation constitute short- and mid-term goals of this important domain.

There has recently been progress in enabling the exploitation of the vast amounts of health-related data available in various repositories. Rich metadata is becoming publicly available, leading to more use of the respective datasets, as researchers outside of the organization that initially collected the data are able to find, access and interpret the data by following the FAIR²¹ principles. Health imaging and radiomics-based correlation studies are emerging showing that imaging biomarkers are powerful prognostic markers of survival e.g., in cancer²². Nougaret et al.²³ summarized in 2019: “Over the last 5 years, more than 500 studies have evaluated the role of radiomics to predict tumour diagnosis, genetic pattern, tumour response to therapy, and survival in multiple cancers. This new post-processing method is aimed at extracting multiple quantitative features from the image and converting them into mineable data.” Large multicentre databases are needed to overcome the limits of radiomics of today to provide robust and reproducible results. Recently, novel AI methodologies have shifted from analysing high-throughput handcrafted imaging features to modelling high-level abstractions in the image using a large number of sequential layers and interconnected units. These so-called Deep Learning (DL) approaches have shown great promise in medical diagnostics delivering performance comparable to healthcare

²⁰ http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/events/ict_bio/2008/docs/200811cancer-model-wkshp-report.pdf

²¹ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

²² Yamamoto S, et al. *Radiology*. 2015;275(2):384-92. doi: 10.1148/radiol.15142698. PubMed PMID: 25734557

²³ Nougaret S et al. *Current Oncology Reports* 2019; 21:70; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11912-019-0815-1>

professionals²⁴.

Driven by the understanding of the enormous potential value of data, there is increasing emphasis in healthcare on unlocking this value by enhancing data quality, and by improving sharing and reuse. However, the current siloed approach to data collection and management, and the disparity of the data limit the value that researchers can extract from data. Even when data is accessible, it is difficult for users to discover and understand the underlying structure and meaning of the datasets, and efficiently process the data for research. To this end, there is a significant need to integrate and harmonize the collected biomedical datasets into vast and sustainable repositories. Enhanced collaboration is as well key to the development of large repositories of high-quality data to support AI, and to the implementation of accurate and clinically impactful AI-based solutions. The adoption of AI in healthcare applications depends on the ability to provide appropriate, privacy-preserving use of data, and to ensure that the outputs are validated, transparent and explainable. Moreover, new solutions must provide a good fit with clinical workflows, and the users need to be adequately trained to use them and to correctly interpret the outputs. All the above challenges need to be addressed in order to streamline the development of meaningful AI solutions and their adoption to accelerate discovery and translation into clinical practice of new and improved diagnosis and treatment options in are diseases.

To be successful Trustworthiness and explainability of AI to stakeholders, especially end-users, are key issues. In the absence of explainability, gaining the trust of the end-users and introducing AI solutions in healthcare is very challenging. The enormous benefits of AI in healthcare will be fully realized when algorithms become interpretable or explainable to their users. The currently existing trust gap is due to the fact that there is no transparency of current state of the art AI algorithms²⁵, although transparency is now a fundamental principle for data processing under the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The European Union has recently (April 2019), issued its “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence”²⁶, whilst in May 2019, forty-two countries adopted the OECD principles on artificial intelligence, the first intergovernmental standard for AI. Within these guidelines, a trustworthy system needs to satisfy a number of requirements²⁷:

1. respecting the rule of law
2. being aligned with agreed ethical principles and values, including privacy, fairness, human dignity
3. keeping us, the humans, in control
4. ensuring the system's behaviour is transparent to us, and
5. its decision-making process is explainable

²⁴ Liu X, et al. Lancet Digital Health 2019; 1e271-297; doi: 10.1016/S2589-7500(19)30123-2

²⁵ Heike Felzmann, et al. Transparency you can trust, Big Data & Society, January–June 2019: 1–14, DOI: 10.1177/2053951719860542

²⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation/guidelines#Top>

²⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

6. and being robust and safe.

In the medical field, trustworthiness of AI methods aiding decisional processes is of paramount importance, considering the impact on patients' safety and the social costs these methods may cause. Therefore, trustworthiness must be addressed in detail. Regardless of the traditional software integrity and verification strategies, AI methods and tools require additional cautions and foresight to avoid significant safety risks and side effects in patient care²⁸ due to their incorrect use or possible incorrect segmentations, classifications and predictions. They have the potential to evolve into a new pillar of instruments of physicians to diagnose and treat patients next to pharmaceuticals, medical devices and bioanalytical systems. As with drugs, clinicians must be aware of the application range and the limitations of an AI system for its safe use on patients. Education and training of clinical and technological staff in healthcare organisations is one answer to this serious issue, beside the regulatory dimension and ongoing research on explainable AI.

In addition, successful projects need to deliver a novel technical infrastructure that will ensure:

- a significant amount of data including imaging, molecular and others available for processing,
- quality for all types of data including imaging data,
- distributed use of AI tools and models,
- increased robustness in models' generalizability and reproducibility, that is depending on the size of the training sets
- optimized model performance in filtered patient cohorts (i.e., geographic areas, scan vendor, level of image distortion, etc.) to improve generalizability, and
- model transparency.

4.4 Legal and Regulatory Framework

In recent years, several new EU regulations were introduced that highlighted the importance of data protection not only in medicine, but especially impacted the day-to-day collection, storage and sharing of medical data. This directly implies such an endeavour as the EU4CHILD ecosystem. This subsection cannot give a complete guide to implement such an ecosystem from a legal and regulatory point of view, rather this subsection aims to list regulations and give a broader view on what has to be taken into account for an implementation plan.

At the point of writing this deliverable, the first half of the year 2021, key regulatory points of the General Data Protection Regulation 679/2016 (GDPR) are still to be implemented on member state level for clinical research use. The impact of the Regulations on Medical Devices 2017/745

²⁸ Carol J. Smith, Designing Trustworthy AI: A Human-Machine Teaming Framework to Guide Development, AAAI FSS-19: Artificial Intelligence in Government and Public Sector, Arlington, Virginia, US, October 2019, arXiv:1910.03515

on bringing AI supported medicine software to the market is currently discussed by data protection officers. Further are clinical trials subject to a change in regulation through the Clinical Trials Regulation 536/2014, applying from May 2021 with a four-year transit period.

The legal and regulatory framework for the EU4CHILD ecosystem must reflect the current legal basis provided through EU regulations but also through national implementations of these regulations.

4.4.1 Data Protection and Privacy

A short introduction to the General Data Protection Regulation 679/2016 (GDPR)²⁹ is written in the publication *From Big Data to Precision Medicine* by Hulsen et al. [16] “The GDPR applies if the data controller (the organization that collects data), data processor (the organization that processes data on behalf of the data controller) or data subject is based in the EU. For science, this means that all studies performed by European institutes/companies and/or on European citizens, will be subject to the GDPR, with the exception of data that is fully anonymized³⁰. The GDPR sets out seven key principles: lawfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimization; accuracy; storage limitation; integrity and confidentiality (security); and accountability. The GDPR puts some constraints on data sharing, e.g., if a data controller wants to share data with another data controller, he/she needs to have an appropriate contract in place, particularly if that other data controller is located outside the EU³¹. If a data controller wants to share data with a third party, and that third party is a processor, then a Data Processor Agreement (DPA) needs to be made. Apart from this DPA, the informed consent that the patient signs before participating in a study, needs to state clearly for what purposes their data will be used³².”

In addition to the high data protection standards by the GDPR, data privacy is considered as well. All natural persons are granted several rights and principles under the GDPR such that organizations are obliged to facilitate these rights³³. Individuals can ask organizations and companies for access to their personal data under Article 15, in case they were collected. Articles 13 and 14 regulated that companies and organizations collecting personal data have to inform individuals about the data collection activities and the legal basis. In case no legal basis is presents, informed consents are required for data collection. With Articles 18, 21 and 17 individuals have the right to object to processing of their personal data, the right to restrict

²⁹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/> last visited 2021/08/25

³⁰ Intersoft Consulting. *Recital 26 - Not Applicable to Anonymous Data*, (2018). Available online at: <https://gdpr-info.eu/recitals/no-26/> last visited 2021/08/25

³¹ Data Protection Network. *GDPR and Data Processing Agreements*, (2018). Available online at: <https://www.dpnetwork.org.uk/gdpr-data-processing-agreements/> last visited 2021/08/25

³² Intersoft Consulting. *Art. 7 GDPR - Conditions for consent*, (2018). Available online at: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-7-gdpr/> last visited 2021/08/25

³³ <https://gdpr.eu/data-privacy/> last visited 2021/08/25

processing of their data in case of e.g., inaccurate data and the right to demand their data to be erased.

4.4.2 Medical Device Regulation

According to current EU regulations, software used for the diagnosis or therapy of patients falls under the term “medical device”. Medical devices within the EU are currently regulated by 3 directives: Council Directive 90/385/EEC2 on Active Implantable Medical Devices (AIMDD) (1990), Council Directive 93/42/EEC3 on Medical Devices (MDD) (1993) and Council Directive 98/79/EC4 on in vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices (IVDMD) (1998). In 2017, two new Regulations were adopted by the Council and the Parliament. The Medical Device Regulation 2017/745 (MDR)³⁴ and the In Vitro Diagnostics Regulation 2017/746 (IVDR)³⁵.

The EU4CHILD ecosystem and the planned prediction *in silico* models falls under the MDR. According to Rule 11 of the MDR, software for medical use can be grouped into classes and must be approved for the chosen class. The text of Rule 11 states the following:

"Software intended to provide information which is used to take decisions with diagnosis or therapeutic purposes is classified as class IIa, except if such decisions have an impact that may cause:

- *Death or an irreversible deterioration of a person's state of health, in which case it is in class III; or*
- *Serious deterioration of a person's state of health or a surgical intervention, in which case it is classified as class IIb.*

*Software intended to monitor physiological processes is classified as class IIa, except if it is intended for monitoring of vital physiological parameters, where the nature of variations of those parameters is such that it could result in immediate danger to the patient, in which case it is classified as class IIb. All other software is classified as class I."*³⁶

Since the prediction *in silico* models can indicate a medical action that can influence a person's state of health, they most likely fall under MDR class IIb or III. The MDR class of the ecosystem platform is difficult to decide. If i.e., an incorrect transmission of patient data could lead to a prediction result that leads to medical action impacting a person's health state, the ecosystem platform could be considered class IIb. This should be checked carefully.

³⁴ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/overview/medical-devices> last visited 2021/08/26

³⁵ <https://euivdr.com/> last visited 2021/08/26

³⁶ <https://johner-institute.com/articles/regulatory-affairs/and-more/mdr-rule-11-software/> last visited 2021/08/26

4.4.3 Clinical Trials Regulation

The Clinical Trials Regulation 536/2014³⁷ will become applicable by the end of January 2022. The regulation will repeal the existing EU Clinical Trials Directive 2001/20/EC and national legislation that was put in place to implement the Directive. It will also apply to trials authorized under the previous legislation if they are still ongoing three years after the Regulation has come into operation. The Regulation harmonizes the assessment and supervision processes for clinical trials throughout the EU, via a Clinical Trials Information System (CTIS). CTIS will contain the centralized EU portal and database for clinical trials foreseen by the Regulation.

The centralized CTIS portal will allow for harmonized electronic submissions for clinical trials conduction within Europe. It is thought to improve the application process, collaboration, information-sharing and decision-making between member states. In addition, the centralized approach will allow for consistent rules for conducting clinical trials throughout the EU.

This regulation, with the before mentioned regulations GDPR and MDR, shape the legal framework of the EU4CHILD ecosystem. The ecosystems have to be designed with data protection and user privacy and patients as a key design philosophy. Developed in silico models have to be tested and validated according to clinical trials guidelines and approved the MDR class system. Moreover, the ecosystems implementation as an online portal has to be validated by software development and UI-UX standards and approved by the MDR rules.

4.5 The Ecosystems Ethics Framework

The ethical considerations for the EU4CHILD ecosystem are broad and cover several areas. First of all is the ecosystem aimed to improve the diagnosis and treatment of children with cancer, which is a vulnerable patient demographic due to their young age, and their families. Information material for children must be grafted carefully using possibly different levels of explanation to reach children in all ages. Families stand under immense stress when a loved child is diagnoses with cancer. This should be taken into account when informing parents about the diagnosis, the treatment and also when asking for consent in order to collect, process and share their child's medical data.

Second are the consideration for the technical implementation of the ecosystem, which could be an online platform. The ethics framework needs to reflect all challenges of potentially storing the children's data in such a platform, that would need to be accessible ideally worldwide to increase the reach for collection important data. New technologies described in Section **Error! Reference source not found.** including differential privacy and swarm learning can allow to limit the risks of data breaches while still enabling learn new and innovative insight into rare diseases.

³⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/health/human-use/clinical-trials/regulation_en

The third area that needs to be addressed from an ethical point of view are prediction models or *in silico* models. These models are required to explain their usage of patient data for training to be transparent according to article 12 of the GDPR. Patients have to be informed whether their medical data could remain part of the trained model. The decision finding process also needs to be explainable and transparent; such that medical decisions can be comprehended by the attending physician. Additionally, software such as *in silico* models fall under the EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR) 2017/745. *In silico* models most likely fall under category 3 of medical devices in the MDR and need to be approved accordingly.

The fourth consideration is the responsibility that results from decision support systems for diagnostics and treatment. **Figure 19** shows a hypothetical case where a physician and an AI system both chose between therapy A or B for the patient at hand. In the ideal case both choose the same and appropriate therapy, as depicted in this Figure. No legal or ethical questions may arise in this case. However, there are two constellations that are ethically and legally unsolved. Starting from the knowledge that treatment A is the correct or best one for the patient, the question is who is responsible if the doctor relies on treatment B as it was suggested by the AI system? And is the physician *more guilty* if he chooses treatment B despite the AI system did choose treatment A? In this case the physician did act against the decision support systems advice. This question of responsibility needs to be solved.

		AI Therapy	
		A	B
Physician Therapy	A	Physician ✓ AI ✓	
	B		Physician ✓ AI ✓

Figure 19. Physician and AI therapy decision matrix. The green color indicates overlapping therapy selection.

The fifth ethical consideration for doctors and medical experts is the normative change in landscape for research use of patient medical data and biological materials. There are considerable differences in research ethics regulations like the Declaration of Helsinki (WMA, 2013), international ethical guideline for health-related research involving humans (CIOMS Guidelines, 2016), the recommendation on research on biological materials of human origin (Council of Europe, 2016) and the GDPR with their national implementation. Where the research ethics guidelines can allow for interventional consent or an informed consent that is specific, dynamic and board, the GDPR only allows for a specific and dynamic informed consent. This limited the use cases of collected medical data under the GDPR informed consent. The German Medizin Informatik Initiative published recently a broad informed consent³⁸ under the GDPR that allows to collect medical patient data in Germany for a broad research use. Similar projects are ongoing in other European countries and the proposed Data Governance Act³⁹ can allow for a general broad consent and facilitate data sharing for research use under the GDPR.

The work by Hulson et al. [16] summarizes the medical research challenges with the GDPR: “While the implementation of GDPR has brought this [data ownership] issue into sharp focus, it has not resolved a fundamental dilemma. As clinicians and scientists, we face an increasingly urgent need to balance the opportunity Big Data provides for improving healthcare, against the right of individuals to control their own data. It is our responsibility to only use data with appropriate consent, but it is also our responsibility to maximize our ability to improve health. Balancing these two will remain an increasing challenge for all precision medicine strategies.”

The before mentioned projects MyPal and EUSTANDS4PM have, among others, written extensive ethics deliverables, which should be mentioned in this context. For MyPal, deliverable D1.1 “MyPal Ethics” is available through CORDIS⁴⁰ and the EUSTANDS4PM have published their deliverable D3.1 “Legal and ethical review of in silico modelling” on their webpage⁴¹.

³⁸ <https://www.medizinformatik-initiative.de/de/mustertext-zur-patienteneinwilligung> last visited 2021/08/25

³⁹ <https://www.embopress.org/doi/full/10.15252/msb.202110229> last visited 2021/08/25

⁴⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825872/results> last visited 2021/08/26

⁴¹ <https://www.eu-stands4pm.eu/publications> last visited 2021/08/26

5 Technical and AI considerations

This chapter describes considerations from a technical point of view for the EU4CHILD ecosystems and the employed AI and machine learning *in silico* models.

5.1 Introduction

The choice of the technical basis for the ecosystem will define how complex the maintenance will be and how widely it can be adopted to different access forms through e.g., a web portal, a desktop application or a mobile application with touch input. Additionally, the technical requirements for the *in silico* models have to be considered from runtime environment to computational power need.

To achieve this, open source⁴² software with open software licenses should be used wherever possible for server side and user side applications. Only open-source software allows to be checked by a wide an independent range of security experts to minimize security risks through software errors. The so-called software stack, which consists of all software parts that are assembled to the EU4CHILD ecosystem, should be selected by their privacy by design and security by design principles. Additionally, reliable software support must be available for all employed software. The state of the art for interoperability and supported data format should be evaluated to ensure a future proof operation. For the interoperability of IT systems, standardized interfaces such as the REST⁴³ are commonly used; current data standards in medicine are e.g., the hl7 FHIR⁴⁴ standard and ICD-10⁴⁵ to only name a few. To match the computational power requirements of deep learning *in silico* models in particular, a scalable IT infrastructure has to be built to not limit users by hardware availability. This infrastructure should use scalable software deployment technologies such as Docker Kubernetes⁴⁶, which allows to make new computational power available automatically if demand is high.

Besides the technical necessities for *in silico* models, they should also be designed to preserve the patient's privacy. Further, the *in silico* models should not be a so-called black box (Reference Rai et al.[17]), where the decision process is not explained, but rather should the inferred prediction result be comprehensible by the attending physician and ideally by the patient.

⁴² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_source last visited 2021/08/27

⁴³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Representational_state_transfer last visited 2021/08/27

⁴⁴ <https://hl7.org/FHIR/> last visited 2021/08/27

⁴⁵ <https://www.who.int/standards/classifications/classification-of-diseases> last visited 2021/08/27

⁴⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kubernetes> last visited 2021/08/27

5.1.1 Related Projects

Projects related to technological and AI considerations in this field are e.g., the Go-FAIR project⁴⁷. The FAIR principles are to improve the **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, and **R**euse of digital assets. For this the project provides guidelines, information material and workshops to educate people that collected, use and store data to apply certain standards such that the data can be found and reused.

The EU funded CORBEL project⁴⁸ researches the collaboration of several biological and medical research infrastructures. The developed shared services for live-science can be used as inspiration on how a platform has to be designed to share data between different stakeholders.

The EU funded project EU-STANDS4PM works on a standardization framework for data integration and data-driven *in silico* models for personalized medicine. They published a harmonized Data Access Agreement⁴⁹ which can reduce hurdles do access already collected data. Additionally, they plan an ISO standardization for *in silico* models, for which no further information is available by the time of writing this document.

5.2 AI Considerations

In this section we will provide a set of related technologies (this is of course not an extensive list, since there are numerous AI techniques proposed in the literature and in the current medical practice) divided into 2 parts: one explaining the learning models and use in health applications for paediatric cancer, and one explaining mechanisms for applying privacy respectful AI. The AI related technologies selection depends on the kind of medical aim pursued, e.g., it is different the technique to be used to perform the analysis of the EHR than the classification of a tumour in a medical image, and the kind of information we are using (e.g., genomic information vs clinical information).

It takes time and effort to find the right approach and model, among the different AI techniques which can be applied to the related problems in childhood cancer. In addition, the data acquisition and selection of data which can be relevant is a task that should be considered as a main element and time-consuming effort in the AI research.

5.2.1 Learning models, from Machine Learning to deep and Reinforcement Learning

Machine learning solutions have been developed for many health-related applications in the past, before the wide adoption of deep learning. Machine Learning is currently used when there is not

⁴⁷<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> last visited 2021/08/27

⁴⁸<https://www.corbel-project.eu/home.html> last visited 2021/08/27

⁴⁹https://www.eu-stands4pm.eu/data_access last visited 2021/08/27

a clear model applicable to our problem or there are not enough data to apply deep learning algorithms that normally require a big set of annotated data.

Deep learning emerged as a novel solution around 10 years ago to improve the accuracy of different problems related to AI and gained a lot of traction with the wide adoption in different markets. Deep Learning is based on Neural Networks with multiple layers which progressively extract higher-level features from the raw input. A wide list of different techniques can be found in the text by Mosavi et al. [12].

Some examples of use for paediatric cancer research are:

Deep Learning Models

- Convolutional Neural Networks: these have been proven strong accuracy for medical image detection and classification, something very relevant in neuroblastoma and nephroblastoma detection.
- Recurrent Neural Networks: these are especially relevant when working with time series, longitudinal data, and are used in speech applications in health.
- AutoEncoders: able to compress data and support a lot of analysis of medical information
- Generative Adversarial Networks: which are useful to generate synthetic data, which is very relevant in paediatric cancer due to the scarcity of samples in AI research as the majority are rare diseases.
- Transformers, which adopts the mechanism of attention, differentially weighing the significance of each part of the input data which are relevant to Natural Language Processing, a technique which is used to extract and understand data from Electronic Health Records.

5.2.2 Privacy Preserving AI Related Techniques:

Another relevant topic in AI is to implement models which can preserve the data privacy and provenance. In many cases, moving medical information outside the hospital to a central cloud is a sensitive issue because of privacy and security concerns.

- Federated Learning
 - A prerequisite for applying any state-of-the-art Machine Learning (ML) algorithmic formulation is to centralize all training data in one machine or a data centre. Within this step, any subsequent Artificial Intelligence (AI) technique is able to build solid models using consecutive data manipulation techniques. However, a key-objective in privacy oriented and security-based applications is to define a trust relation between the parties that exchange data. Federated Learning (FL) (Konečný et al. [13]) is acknowledged as the next big thing within the context of AI / deep learning, where it enables different entities to

collaboratively learn a shared model while simultaneously storing all the training data into their local devices. Consequently, FL approaches overcome the major limitation of data centralization and storing in the cloud. As a result, we can today rely on federated counterparts. Projecting to the case of medical applications, FL enables health-organizations located at different geographical locations to collaboratively develop AI models, while providing no direct access to the potentially sensitive or classified client's data.

- Swarm Learning
 - Swarm learning dispenses with a dedicated server parameters via the Swarm network and builds the models independently on private data at the individual sites, as well as providing security measures to support data sovereignty, security, and confidentiality. This is done following private permissioned blockchain technology, used to transfer the trained parameters, which is thought to be as a trust mechanism, such that the source of ill-intentioned parameters can be identified through the blockchain (Warnat-Herresthal et al. [14]).
- Differential Privacy
 - Differential privacy mathematically guarantees that anyone seeing the result of a differentially private analysis will make the same inference about any individual's private information, whether or not that individual's private information is included in the input to the analysis. Only relevant data, that do not offer too much information about an individual, is shared. For example, only parts of an image or certain region of a genome. Reference Wei et al. [15].

5.2.3 Explainable AI

Artificial intelligence (AI) is gaining a lot of attraction due to the great ability to solve problems which were impossible to be solved few years ago. In healthcare it is increasingly entering the mainstream medical practice and supporting human decisions which are affecting patients care. However, the effectiveness of these systems is limited by the machine's inability to explain its thoughts and actions to human users in these critical situations. This is especially critical within the integrated care of children where guidance of the treatment, care or support when using AI models should be carefully examined.

Exploitability become critical specially when addressing Deep Learning techniques since it is using Deep Neural Networks which are difficult to fully interpret the determination of a cause by humans, due to the structure and large number of operations involved.

How can decisions of AI be explained to physicians, patients (children) or even to caregivers? This is a question that should be considered in the balance between best performing deep neural

network-based models and capability of explanation of the decisions made, to avoid acting as black-box entities.

5.3 Technical Consideration

The technical foundation of IT systems such as the here described EU4CHILD ecosystem is a crucial decision, since it cannot easily be changed once the system is deployed. For this, we discuss here three design topics, which are of particular importance to IT systems with the intended goal of performing *in silico* predictions results on personal data. However, the whole ecosystem should be considered for the actual implementation. A comprehensive list can unfortunately not be given in this document, since technology and the state of the art in software engineering is a very fast-moving object.

5.3.1 Prediction Models as a Service

Although the term “as a service” has become increasingly associated to entities that are not know for preserving the privacy of their users, but rather using their personal information as a business model, this design decision can allow to increase data security while making the ecosystem more flexibility at the same time.

If a prediction model is offered as a service by the data processor, the data controller has full control over the data sent to the model and the degree of pseudonymization. This enables the data controller to keep their patients identifying link between pseudonym and real name on their premises, which reduces the risk and the severeness of a potential data breach compared to centralized pseudonymization services.

The offered model as a service could be provided by a research institute or commercial AI service provider, which distributes the required computation power over several instances. In this scenario, a particular demanding use case would not block all the available compute resources of a centralized system and allows the other decentralized systems to be available for other users. Additionally, incidences such as a data breach or technical failures would only affect a small number of users, as no centralized service was affected.

5.3.2 Prediction Model Framework

If an IT system would offer *in silico* models as a service, a common technical ground has to provided, such that all models adhere to a defined set of rules and conditions. The technical basis for *in silico* models is diverse due to the different programming languages used to implement them. Deep Learning frameworks are e.g., TensorFlow⁵⁰, TORCH/PyTorch⁵¹ or CAFFE⁵² to only

⁵⁰ <https://www.tensorflow.org/> last visited 2021/08/27

⁵¹ <https://pytorch.org/> last visited 2021/08/27

⁵² <https://caffe.berkeleyvision.org/> last visited 2021/08/27

name a few. A common Machine Learning framework is scikit-learn⁵³, of which many more exist. For pharmacokinetics pharmacodynamics modelling the tool NONMEN⁵⁴ can be used among others. Models developed with these frameworks and tools require certain software to be available in order to operate. A so-called Model Runtime Environment (MRE) can provide these technical requirements.

The MRE provides a predefined list of software, which will be updated regularly, and can be installed from each model service provider. Additionally, the MRE has a standardized interface that can be used by clinics or clinicians to send their patient data to the model and retrieve the prediction results. Further is the available compute power distributed over the requested predictions by the MRE.

Two different approaches are available to implement a MRE:

- The *in silico* model is delivered to the MRE in a so-called container⁵⁵. In this scenario a closed system is delivered to the MRE containing the model itself and the required software. This enables the highest flexibility. The MRE provides only the communication interface towards the model and towards the users.
- Only the *in silico* model is delivered to the MRE. In this scenario the software required to run the models needs to be installed by the MRE, in addition to the communication capabilities towards the models and the user. This allows the MRE to have full control over the installed software and thus limit technical and security issues. However, the models are limited to the supported software.

5.3.3 Security Requirements

The EU4CHILD ecosystem will provide the possibility for clinics and clinicians to access a decision support system. These systems contain prediction models, which can predict a treatment outcome or diagnostics given patient data as input. Access to the prediction models will be provided by the ecosystem either as a service or can be installed on-site at a clinic using a prediction model framework. Since models are a highly specialized computer programs, they carry the same risk as all other computer programs. Possible security scenarios could be a programming error in a model, resulting in a security vulnerability, or the intended inclusion of malicious code in the model. The EU4CHILD ecosystem must have a procedure to check for these security risks to avoid a leak of patient data. Additionally, the MRE has to be designed to protect connected hospital information systems against ransomware attacks⁵⁶ and supply chain attacks⁵⁷.

⁵³ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/> last visited 2021/08/27

⁵⁴ <https://www.iconplc.com/innovation/nonmem/> last visited 2021/08/27

⁵⁵ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Docker_\(software\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Docker_(software)) last visited 2021/08/27

⁵⁶ <https://securityintelligence.com/articles/health-care-ransomware-strains-hospitals-in-crosshairs/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.techrepublic.com/article/kaseya-supply-chain-attack-impacts-more-than-1000-companies/>

5.4 Data Collection

This subsection focuses on technical challenges of data storage and data sharing of medical data from children with cancer. Data categories can be imaging data, EHRs, PROs, results from tissues samples, genetic data, hemograms and others. Although the disease category *childhood cancer* is subsumed under rare diseases, the approach and tools of Big Data⁵⁸ does still apply. Even if the number of individuals affected by this disease is relatively low the amount of data collected from each individual is vast and increases with new diagnostic tools and procedures and advances in imaging technologies. The design of a scalable data storage system with fast analysis tools and easy to use access for data sharing is crucial.

5.4.1 Data Storage and Analysis

Although the authors of the document suggested to use of open-source software for the EU4CHILD ecosystems software stack, it is difficult to adhere to this rule for data storage. A data storage solution should always be tailored for the kind of data that need to be stored. Since several different data types such as text, data tables, DNA and RNA sequences and imaging data will be used, an open-source solution could not achieve the same performance and scalability.

The storage of any kind of data can be done with MongoDB⁵⁹, which was initially designed to store large data such as video material. Some data should be stored in specialized databases such as PostgreSQL⁶⁰ for relational data such as EHR, PROs and hemograms. Even more specialized data bases exist such as GenBank⁶¹, which is database for genetic sequence database, an annotated collection of all publicly available DNA sequences.

For the analysis of text, from EHRs and doctor letters, the tool Apache OpenNLP⁶² can be used. It is a machine learning library-based toolkit for the processing not natural language text. OpenNLP supports the most common NLP tasks, such as tokenization, sentence segmentation, part-of-speech tagging, named entity extraction, chunking, parsing, language detection and coreference resolution. The Apache Hadoop project⁶³ is a framework that allows for the distributed processing of large data sets across clusters of computers using simple programming models. It is designed to scale up from single servers to thousands of machines, each offering local computation and storage.

The field of data storage and analysis is complex and should be designed by experts with the precise use case, data and requirements in mind.

⁵⁸ <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.695.5308&rep=rep1&type=pdf> last visited 2021/08/30

⁵⁹ <https://www.mongodb.com/> last visited 2021/08/30

⁶⁰ <https://www.postgresql.org/> last visited 2021/08/30

⁶¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/> last visited 2021/08/30

⁶² <https://opennlp.apache.org/> last visited 2021/08/30

⁶³ <https://hadoop.apache.org/> last visited 2021/08/30

5.4.2 Data Sharing

To avoid ethical, legal and administrative issues of medical data sharing, the before mentioned technologies federated learning and swarm learning can be used. Federated Learning is a machine learning technique that trains an algorithm across multiple decentralized edge devices or servers holding local data samples. Swarm learning is similar to this with the addition of a block chain, which is used to exchange ML results from each participant. The data never leave the premises of the clinics with both technologies, such that patient confidentiality has increased security compared to solutions where the actual data is shared.

A disadvantage of decentralized ML training approaches is that data scientists cannot investigate the data if an error accrues or use the data for other approaches than initial described. The data have to be prepared and made available to fit the needs of federated learning or swarm learning approaches. This limits the possibility of data scientists to react fast to issues or implement new ideas immediate, since they have wait for the data providers to source new data or transform into a new form if required.

In the case that medical data can be shared directly, a common format for the data has to be agreed upon. For this the already mentioned data formats hl7 FHIR or ICD-10 can be used. With all the data available to the data scientist, they can more efficiently adopt new ideas and find errors. Before the data can be made available, a pseudonymization technology has to be used to replace identifying information with pseudonyms. This is ethically challenging, since even for example data of genetic material carries the identity of patients and could not be used to their full potential if masked sufficiently.

6 High-level Insights: Local and international politics

Ultimately, EU4CHILD aims to increase the political commitment for childhood cancer diagnosis and treatment at local, regional, national and EU levels, supporting regulators, policy and decision-makers in receiving understandable, AI based, information able to inform their own decision-making process and also the development of high-quality cancer policy and organizational regulations to ensure early and accurate diagnosis and effective treatment of childhood and adolescent cancer.

From a policy perspective, policy and decision-makers are driven by the need to improve the access, coverage and quality of health systems and healthcare delivery for childhood cancer from a value-based perspective. This ambition boils down to **improving the outcomes of childhood cancer while limiting the costs**, a goal for which the EU has set in motion a high-level strategy built upon the Europe's Beating Cancer plan⁶⁴ and its flagship initiative *Helping Children with Cancer*.

Within this plan, a series of **policy priorities** and **needs** are defined⁶⁵:

- Reaching a deeper understanding the complexity of childhood cancer.
- Leveraging the standard of care across Europe.
- Aligning EU health policy strategies across Member States in the path towards a European Health Union.
- Focusing on improving health promotion, training and awareness in the EU.

The answer lies in two other questions: *how to further meaningful, collaborative research on cancer*, and *how to effectively streamline results into actionable insights to inform policy decisions?*

For both, data is the solution. However, the healthcare sector (at the EU and global stage) is rich in data but poor in information, and there is a distinct lack of evidence-based information to inform policy decisions and regulations. This is a critical setback for policy makers, since arriving at coherent, cohesive and exhaustive policy directives is no easy task. The magnitude of the problem is amplified in such a fragmented, unconnected scenario as the health data space for childhood cancer. Additionally, childhood cancer is effectively a rare disease that affects a very vulnerable population, and thus suffers from greater data scarcity and much more pressing concerns regarding health data exchange, informed consent, privacy and confidentiality.

⁶⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life/european-health-union/cancer-plan-europe_en last visited 2021/09/03

⁶⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/default/files/non_communicable_diseases/docs/eu_cancer_plan_en.pdf last visited 2021/09/03

While AI methods can help break through this issue by extracting valuable information from all this ‘dormant’ health data; it also introduces a new set of challenges for decision-makers, mainly revolving around the technical intricacy and inherent opaqueness that it brings to the table.

Understanding how AI methods actually works (i.e., how a given AI algorithm arrives at a conclusion) is, in some cases, simply not possible due to the way AI operates and its usual ‘black-box’ approach.

Consequently, making the **technical dimension of AI understandable and accessible** for a wider, multi-disciplinary audience is a fundamental step in what EU4CHILD intends to accomplish. Within the policy realm, this ambition will materialize into providing policy makers with the **necessary tools and sufficient knowledge** to:

- Recognize potential risks and biases in AI.
- Understand the importance of exploring new ‘white-box’ approaches that reinforce explainability and transparency of AI.
- Grow into the role of ‘ambassadors’ of AI, helping build trust among healthcare professionals, providers and the general public.
- Provide funding for infrastructure and enabling tools.
- Evaluate technology deployment and maintenance costs.
- Assess the expected impact of any intervention through quantifiable means, supported by guidelines and quality assurance schemes.

However, there is another layer of complexity: the ramifications of these needs show different nuances at different levels of policy making and enforcing. EU4CHILD will actively work to address these disparities:

- **At EU level:** actively communicating and disseminating on EU4CHILD’s AI ecosystem and framework, producing and sharing advocacy materials to reach a multi-disciplinary audience (technical, clinical, political) that can enrich the project’s vision and reach.
- **At local, regional or national level:** recommendations for the translation from EU policy and recommendations in national, regional or local contexts. Identifying the differential needs of policy and decision makers regarding AI according to their level of competences. Additionally, supporting case studies and implementation plans through policy briefs, recommendations and best practices to assess the actual feasibility of integrating AI in childhood and adolescents (both living with it and survivors) current cancer care pathways (i.e., how to address specific roadblocks on data sharing, data protection, privacy regulations?).

Additional needs and suggestions will be gathered through field work research to be implemented with key stakeholders over the Fall 2021 and Spring 2022, in close collaboration between WP4 and WP2.

7 Conclusions and Summary

This document presents the user requirements of the stakeholders *IT professionals and data scientists* and *Clinicians and medical professionals* drawn from literature research in Chapter Methodology3. Both stakeholder groups suggest the creation of research networks between clinics to increase patient cohorts to improve the statistical robustness of developed *in silico* models. This could be facilitated through data exchange contracts between clinics to allow each participant equal access for their AI research. *Clinicians and medical professionals* demand a solid foundation for the research from basic scientists to improve research success. *IT professionals and data scientists* demand the clinics to adhere to data standards for the collection of data.

Results from the questionnaire show that stakeholders from *Society as whole, IT professionals and data scientists* and *Clinicians and medical professionals* are willing to participate with their children in AI supported clinical studies for development of AI supported decision support systems. Most respondents would share tissue samples from their child while some showed the requirement for a clear benefit. From this result and the free text comments from respondents, actions could be derived.

The document discusses key medical issues that motivate the development of AI systems in medicine to further improve life expectancy of childhood cancer in Chapter 4. The ethical and regulatory hurdles for the use of data driven technologies are also discussed with an introduction to the most influential EU regulations on this topic. Although this chapter cannot provide an exhaustive review of the field, it is an introduction that provides the reader an overview of the topic.

Chapter 5 presents key technical and AI considerations that must be met for a decision support system such as the EU4CHILD ecosystem. Several state-of-the-art AI technologies are presented and their advantages for a privacy preserving approach. The ideal technical foundation of the ecosystem is described in this chapter with explanations of limiting factors and design decisions that should be made to adhere to state of the art in technologies, interoperability, privacy and security.

Ultimately, EU4CHILD aims to increase the political commitment for childhood cancer diagnosis and treatment at local, regional, national and EU level, supporting regulators, policy and decision-makers in receiving understandable, AI based, information able to inform their own decision-making processes and also the development of high-quality cancer policy and organizational regulations to ensure early and accurate diagnosis and effective treatment of childhood and adolescent cancer.

8 Outlook

To further consolidate the user needs and requirements of the EU4CHILD ecosystem, the continuous distribution of the questionnaire is planned. Additionally, interviews, focus groups, design thinking sessions or Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) will be evaluated as methods to reach larger samples of stakeholder groups such as policy makers and patient or parent association representatives and increase the reach towards clinicians. Through these social research methods additional assessment of the already identified requirements and needs of each profile of stakeholder will be reassessed and/or confirmed. Moreover, the exploitation strategy will be connected to this research, being implemented in the different country sites of EU4CHILD consortium meetings. Since travel activities are still limited for the consortium members, online equivalents will be considered as well.

The actions identified through the questionnaire findings will be considered for the course of the EU4CHILD project. Differences of perceived knowledge in AI by the stakeholders or the abstention of Citizen respondents in the items regarding data protection regulations will be further analysed. The possibility for information material or educational campaigns will be discussed.

Topics of medical and ethical considerations for this project will be a focus of the consortium, :

- Hurdles in data sharing. How can the hurdles be reduced with data sharing contracts and new data privacy preserving technologies?
- Informed consent. Under the current EU regulations, a broad consent is difficult to achieve. A German initiative has made such a document available for the use in Germany. It should be evaluated if this is possible for other European member states.
- Reach out to ethics committees^{66,67} to understand their level of knowledge in AI. Since ethics committees must approve medical research towards AI applications, their level of knowledge should be understood.

The High-level insights will focus on understanding the needs of policy and decision makers, taking into account their respective competence levels, in order to include in the paediatric cancer AI platform Roadmap, the information that may be required for supporting evidence-based decision making.

⁶⁶ https://hadea.ec.europa.eu/index_en

⁶⁷ <http://www.eurecnet.org/partners/board.html>

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Appendix

This appendix contains information, documents and material in reference to this document.

Questionnaire

As part of this deliverable, a questionnaire was distributed online. The paper version of this questionnaire can be found below in 5 languages English, Spanish, German, French and Italian.

General Questionnaire on Data Protection in Childhood Cancer

English version

Welcome!

Dear Sir or Madam,

This questionnaire is conducted by the team of Prof. Dr. Norbert Graf of the University of Saarland. For the EU-funded project EU4CHILD, we are exploring how Artificial Intelligence (AI) can improve the treatment of children with cancer.

The aim of our project is to collect necessary requirements for an ecosystem in which medical data can be provided for research and evaluated by means of artificial intelligence. The ecosystem should help doctors improve treatment for children with a tumor or leukemia through AI-supported software.

The survey is completely anonymous. No personal data will be asked as part of this questionnaire. Please do not fill in any identifying information about yourself in the free text fields.

First, we would like to learn more about you and how you view the current state of data protection in research

What is your birth year?* *(Text, single line)*

What is your gender?* *(Single choice)*

Male

- Female
- Diverse
- N/A

In what capacity are you answering this questionnaire? You are...* *(Single choice)*

- From the healthcare sector

↳ **So your background is in the healthcare sector. You are... *** *(Single choice)*

- A medical professional
- A healthcare provider (e.g. health ministry, hospital administration)
- Other

↳ **You answered 'Other'. Please specify*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- From research or data science

↳ **So your background is in research or data science. You are... *** *(Single choice)*

- A Data Scientist
- A Basic Scientist (e.g. biology, genetics, pharmacy)
- Other

↳ **You answered 'Other'. Please, specify *** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- A civil or public servant

↳ **So you hold a public position. You are... *** *(Single choice)*

- A Policy Maker
- A Policy Enforcer (e.g. data protection officer)
- A member of a Patient Organization
- Other

↳ **You answered 'Other'. Please specify*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- A citizen

Other

↳ You answered 'Other'. Please specify* (Text, multiple lines)

I do not want to give any information

How would you rate your knowledge of Artificial Intelligence and its application in your area of expertise?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Choose a value from 1 (Very Poor) to 7 (Very Good)

Do you believe that tools or models using Artificial Intelligence will be helpful in medicine?* (Single choice)

No

↳ You answered 'No'. Do you see more risks in Artificial Intelligence than benefits?* (Single choice)

Yes

No

N/A

Only in diagnostics

Only in treatment

In diagnostics and treatment

Do you know any reporting guidelines in medicine using Artificial Intelligence?* (Single choice)

Yes

↳ Are you familiar with any of the following reporting guidelines?* (Multiple choice)

CONSORT AI

SPIRIT AI guidelines

Other

↘ You answered 'Other'. Please list all reporting guidelines you are familiar with below* (Text, multiple lines)

- None of the above
- No
- N/A

Are you aware of any tools and protocols for medical data sharing?* (Single choice)

Yes

↘ Are you familiar with any of the following tools and protocols?* (Multiple choice)

- The FAIR principles
- Federated Learning
- Swarm Learning
- Differential privacy
- Blockchain
- Other

↘ You answered 'Other'. Please list all tools you are familiar with below* (Text, multiple lines)

- None of the above
- No
- N/A

In general, how likely do you consider that medical records are kept confidential...

... in everyday clinical practice?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Choose a value from 1 (I have no confidence in data protection)

to 7 (I have complete confidence in data protection)

... in research projects?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Choose a value from 1 (I have no confidence in data protection)
to 7 (I have complete confidence in data protection)

Do you have children?* (Single choice)

Yes

↳ How important do you consider it to be that your child's medical records are kept confidential...

... in clinical practice?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Choose a value from 1 (I have no confidence that the data will be kept confidential)
to 7 (I have complete confidence that the data will be kept confidential)

... in research projects?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Choose a value from 1 (I have no confidence that the data will be kept confidential)
to 7 (I have complete confidence that the data will be kept confidential)

No

N/A

Do you think that the health data protection regulations that exist today are adequate?* (Single choice)

Yes

No

↳ You answered 'No'. Please, tell us why* (Text, multiple lines)

N/A

Do you believe that privacy regulations are delaying research results?* *(Single choice)*

Yes

↳ **You answered 'Yes'. Please, tell us why*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

No

N/A

Let us imagine that you are living the following situation:

You are the parent of a child who has been diagnosed with an inoperable brain tumour (brainstem tumor). You have been informed by the treating paediatric oncologists that the prognosis of the disease is very poor and that no cure is possible with conventional therapies. Since the treatment and prognosis of this disease has not changed fundamentally in the last 30 years, you will be introduced to a research project in which you can help to develop an AI system that could improve the treatment of brain stem tumors.

For this, all possible data of your child from symptoms to laboratory values, pathological data, genetic data of the tumor and imaging data (CT, MRI) are needed to create a model of the tumor in order to find individual and new therapy options. These data must first be collected from many children with the same disease in order to process and evaluate them in the research project. The hope is that this may lead to a new treatment option for your child.

Would you provide your child's relevant pseudonymized data for research in the described context?* *(Single choice)*

A pseudonym is an arbitrarily chosen sequence of numbers and letters. The pseudonym is used instead of the patient's actual name or patient number and serves to conceal the identity. The connection between the pseudonym and the patient's name is stored in the treating hospital, but is not passed on. Data in pseudonymous form can thus not be directly linked to patients.

Yes

↳ **Would you still provide your child's relevant pseudonymized data for research if the prognosis was significantly better?*** *(Single choice)*

Yes

No

↳ You answered 'No'. Please, tell us why* *(Text, multiple lines)*

N/A

No

↳ You answered 'No'. Please, tell us why* *(Text, multiple lines)*

N/A

Would you have a tissue sample taken from your child for molecular genetic analysis of the tumor and provide this data for research purposes? You have been informed that the result of the analysis may be of no significance for your child, but will in principle provide new insights into this tumor. You also know that genetic data cannot be anonymized* *(Single choice)*

Yes

No

↳ You answered 'No'. Please, tell us why* *(Text, multiple lines)*

N/A

Now, let's imagine another situation:

A childhood cancer research project was successful. An AI system for the treatment of brainstem tumors was developed.

Initial research results indicate that the use of the AI based system has a better prognosis than conventional treatment methods. However, the system has yet to be validated, as the actual benefit needs to be further assessed.

What are your conditions to participate with your child in such a study?* *(Single choice)*

- None
- I need to understand the IT supported system
- I must understand the IT supported system and it should have an identifiable benefit for my child
- I will definitely participate because the prognosis with conventional treatment is too poor
- I will definitely participate because I support research in principle

Other

↳ **You chose 'Other'. Please, specify*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Do you have any other comments you'd like to share with us? *(Text, multiple lines)*

We greatly appreciate your participation and contribution for a better diagnosis and treatment of paediatric cancer!

General Questionnaire on Data Protection in Childhood Cancer

Spanish version

¡Bienvenido!

Este cuestionario está planteado y supervisado por el Prof. Dr. Norbert Graf de la Universidad de Saarland. En el marco del proyecto europeo EU4CHILD nos dedicamos a explorar cómo la Inteligencia Artificial (IA) puede mejorar el tratamiento de niños con cáncer.

El objetivo de nuestro proyecto consiste en reunir todos los requisitos y necesidades de los diferentes actores del ecosistema de cáncer pediátrico, con la idea de facilitar la compartición y evaluación de datos médicos para investigación mediante el uso de IA. Este ecosistema será una gran ayuda para que los profesionales médicos puedan, a través de soluciones basadas en IA, mejorar el tratamiento de niños con algún tipo de tumor o leucemia.

Este cuestionario es completamente anónimo. En ningún momento se solicitarán datos personales. Por favor, no proporciones información que pueda identificarte en los campos de texto libre.

Antes de empezar, queremos conocerte un poco mejor y saber cuál es tu opinión sobre la protección de datos en investigación

¿En qué año naciste?* *(Text, single line)*

¿Cuál es tu género?* *(Single choice)*

- Hombre
- Mujer
- Otro
- N/A

¿Desde qué perspectiva participas en este cuestionario? Eres...* *(Single choice)*

- Del sector sanitario

↘ **Perteneces al sector sanitario. En concreto, eres...*** *(Single choice)*

- Un profesional médico
- Un proveedor de servicios sanitarios (ej. representante de un Ministerio de Sanidad, administración hospitalaria...)
- Otro

↘ **Tu respuesta fue 'Otro'. Por favor, danos más detalles*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- Del mundo de la investigación o el tratamiento de datos

↘ **Perteneces al mundo de la investigación o el tratamiento de datos. En concreto, eres...*** *(Single choice)*

- Un Data Scientist o desarrollador
- Investigador científico (ej. biología, genética, farmacología...)
- Otro

↘ **Tu respuesta fue 'Otro'. Por favor, danos más detalles*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- Del ámbito de la administración pública

↘ **Perteneces al ámbito de la administración pública. En concreto...*** *(Single choice)*

- Te dedicas a crear nuevas políticas y ayudar a la toma de decisiones
- Te dedicas a implementar nuevas políticas (ej. Data Protection Officer)
- Perteneces a una asociación de pacientes
- Otro

↘ **Tu respuesta fue 'Otro'. Por favor, danos más detalles*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- Un ciudadano

- Otro

↘ **Tu respuesta fue 'Otro'. Por favor, danos más detalles*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- No quiero dar esta información

¿Cómo valorarías tus nociones sobre Inteligencia Artificial y su aplicación a tu área de conocimiento?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Elige un valor entre 1 (Muy Bajo) y 7 (Muy Alto)

¿Crees que las herramientas o modelos basados en Inteligencia Artificial serán útiles en medicina?* (Single choice)

- No
- ↳ **Tu respuesta fue 'No'. ¿Piensas que la Inteligencia Artificial tiene más riesgos que beneficios?*** (Single choice)
- Sí
- No
- No lo sé
- Sólo en la fase de diagnóstico
- Sólo en la fase de tratamiento
- Tanto en la fase de diagnóstico como la de tratamiento

¿Conoces alguna directiva, informes o políticas en medicina que utilicen Inteligencia Artificial?* (Single choice)

- Sí
- ↳ **¿Te resulta familiar alguno de las siguientes directivas o políticas?*** (Multiple choice)
- CONSORT AI
- Guidelines de SPIRIT AI
- Otro
- ↳ **Tu respuesta fue 'Otro'. Por favor, lista todas las directivas o políticas que conozcas aquí*** (Text, multiple lines)

Ninguna de las anteriores

No

N/A

¿Conoces alguna herramienta o protocolo para compartición y transferencia de datos médicos?*
(Single choice)

Sí

↳ **¿Te resulta familiar alguna de las siguientes herramientas o protocolos?*** (Multiple choice)

Principios FAIR

Federated Learning

Swarm Learning

Differential privacy

Blockchain

Otro

↳ **Tu respuesta fue 'Otro'. Por favor, lista todas las herramientas que conozcas aquí*** (Text, multiple lines)

Ninguna de las anteriores

No

N/A

En general, ¿cómo valorarías la importancia de preservar la confidencialidad de los datos médicos...

... en la práctica clínica habitual?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Elige un valor entre 1 (No confío en los protocolos de protección de datos) y 7 (Confío plenamente en los protocolos de protección de datos)

... en proyectos de investigación?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Elige un valor entre 1 (No confío en los protocolos de protección de datos) y 7 (Confío plenamente en los protocolos de protección de datos)

¿Tienes hijos?* (Single choice)

Sí

↳ ¿Cómo valorarías la importancia de que los datos médicos de tu hijo/a se mantengan confidenciales...

... en la práctica clínica?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Elige un valor entre 1 (No confío en que los datos se mantengan confidenciales) y 7 (Tengo plena confianza en que los datos serán confidenciales)

... en proyectos de investigación?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Elige un valor entre 1 (No confío en que los datos se mantengan confidenciales) y 7 (Tengo plena confianza en que los datos serán confidenciales)

No

N/A

¿Crees que la regulación vigente para la protección de datos médicos es adecuada?* (Single choice)

Sí

No

↳ Tu respuesta fue 'No'. Por favor, danos más detalles* (Text, multiple lines)

No lo sé

¿Crees que la regulación en temas de privacidad de datos está retrasando la generación de resultados en investigación?* *(Single choice)*

Sí

↳ **Tu respuesta fue 'Sí'. Por favor, danos más detalles*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

No

No lo sé

Imaginemos ahora que te encuentras en la siguiente situación

Eres el padre/madre de un niño/a al que se le ha diagnosticado un tumor cerebral inoperable (tumor de tronco encefálico). Los oncólogos pediatras que lo tratan te han informado de que el pronóstico de la enfermedad es muy malo y no es posible la curación con las terapias convencionales. Dado que el tratamiento y el pronóstico de esta enfermedad no ha cambiado significativamente en los últimos 30 años, se te ofrece la posibilidad de participar en un proyecto de investigación en el que puedes ayudar a desarrollar un sistema de Inteligencia Artificial que podría mejorar el tratamiento de los tumores de tronco encefálico.

Para ello, necesitan todos los datos posibles de tu hijo/a, desde sus síntomas hasta sus pruebas de laboratorio, datos patológicos, datos genéticos del tumor y datos de imagen médica (TAC, RMN) para crear un modelo del tumor que permita encontrar una nueva opción terapéutica individualizada. El proyecto recopilará estos datos de muchos otros niños con la misma enfermedad para primero poder procesarlos y evaluarlos, con la esperanza es que todo esto pueda conducir a una nueva alternativa para el tratamiento de tu hijo/a.

¿Darías tu consentimiento al uso de los datos pseudonimizados de tu hijo/a para la investigación en este contexto?* *(Single choice)*

Un seudónimo es una secuencia de números y letras elegida arbitrariamente. El seudónimo se utiliza en lugar del nombre real del paciente o del número de paciente y sirve para ocultar su identidad. La conexión entre el seudónimo y el nombre del paciente se almacena en la clínica tratante, pero no se transmite. Por tanto, los datos en forma de seudónimo no pueden asignarse directamente a los pacientes.

Sí

↳ **¿Darías tu consentimiento al uso de los datos pseudonimizados de tu hijo/a para la investigación si el pronóstico del tumor fuera significativamente mejor?*** *(Single choice)*

- Sí
 No

↘ Tu respuesta fue 'No'. Por favor, danos más detalles* *(Text, multiple lines)*

- N/A

- No

↘ Tu respuesta fue 'No'. Por favor, danos más detalles* *(Text, multiple lines)*

- N/A

¿Darías tu consentimiento a la toma de una muestra de tejido de tu hijo/a para realizar un análisis genético molecular del tumor y después facilitar los resultados a la investigación? Has sido informado de que el resultado del análisis puede no ser significativo para tu hijo/a, pero en principio ayudará a conocer mejor las características de este tumor. También has sido informado de que los datos genéticos no pueden anonimizarse* *(Single choice)*

- Sí
 No

↘ Tu respuesta fue 'No'. Por favor, danos más detalles* *(Text, multiple lines)*

- N/A

Ahora, imaginemos otra situación

Un proyecto de investigación en cáncer pediátrico ha desarrollado con éxito un sistema basado en Inteligencia Artificial para el tratamiento del tumor de tronco encefálico.

Los resultados preliminares indican que el uso de este sistema de IA mejora el pronóstico de la enfermedad comparado con tratamientos convencionales. Sin embargo, el sistema aún tiene que ser validado, dado que el análisis de sus ventajas reales requiere de una evaluación más detallada.

¿Cuáles son tus condiciones para participar con tu hijo/a en un estudio de estas características?*

(Single choice)

- Ninguna
- Necesito entender el sistema
- Necesito entender el sistema y debe tener un beneficio claro para mi hijo/a
- Participaré seguro porque el pronóstico con tratamientos convencionales es muy desfavorable
- Participaré seguro porque estoy a favor de la investigación por principios
- Otro

↘ **Tu respuesta fue 'Otro'. Por favor, danos más detalles*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Si quieres compartir algún otro comentario con nosotros, puedes hacerlo aquí *(Text, multiple lines)*

¡Muchas gracias por tu colaboración! Tus repuestas contribuirán a mejorar el diagnóstico y tratamiento del cáncer pediátrico

General Questionnaire on Data Protection in Childhood Cancer

French version

Bienvenue !

Cette enquête est menée par le professeur Norbert Graf de l'université de la Sarre. Dans le cadre du projet EU4CHILD financé par l'UE, nous étudions comment l'Intelligence Artificielle (IA) peut améliorer le traitement des enfants atteints de cancer. L'objectif de notre projet est de rassembler les exigences et les besoins d'un écosystème dans lequel les données médicales peuvent être mises à disposition pour la recherche et évaluées à l'aide de l'Intelligence Artificielle. L'écosystème a pour but d'aider les médecins à améliorer le traitement des enfants atteints d'une tumeur ou d'une leucémie grâce à des logiciels assistés par l'IA.

L'enquête est totalement anonyme. Aucune donnée personnelle n'est demandée dans le cadre de ce questionnaire. Veuillez ne pas saisir d'information permettant de vous identifier dans les champs de texte libre.

Tout d'abord, nous aimerions en savoir plus sur vous et savoir comment vous percevez l'état actuel de la protection des données dans la recherche.

Quelle est votre année de naissance ? * *(Text, single line)*

Quel est votre sexe ? * *(Single choice)*

- Homme
- Femme
- Divers
- Non spécifié

Quel est votre domaine d'expertise ou avec quel bagage répondez-vous à ce questionnaire ? *
(Single choice)

- Secteur de la santé
 - ↳ **Vous appartenez au secteur de la santé. Vous êtes...*** *(Single choice)*
 - Un professionnel de la santé

Un administrateur dans le secteur des soins de santé (par exemple, ministère de la santé, administration hospitalière)

Autre

↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Autre'. Veuillez indiquer votre domaine d'expertise*** (Text, multiple lines)

Secteur de la recherche ou de l'informatique

↳ **Vous travaillez dans la recherche ou l'informatique. Vous êtes...*** (Single choice)

Un informaticien ou développeur de modèles

Un chercheur fondamental (par exemple, en biologie, en génétique, en pharmacie)

Autre

↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Autre'. Veuillez indiquer votre domaine d'expertise*** (Text, multiple lines)

Depuis une position publique

↳ **Vous occupez une position publique. Vous êtes...*** (Single choice)

Un décideur politique

Un responsable de la protection des données

Un membre d'une association de patients

Autre

↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Autre'. Veuillez indiquer votre domaine d'expertise*** (Text, multiple lines)

En tant que citoyen

Autre

↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Autre'. Veuillez indiquer votre domaine d'expertise*** (Text, multiple lines)

Je ne veux pas donner d'informations

Comment évaluez-vous votre connaissance de l'Intelligence Artificielle et de son application dans votre domaine ? * *(1-7 Likert scale)*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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Dans la fourchette de 1 (très mauvais) à 7 (très bon)

Pensez-vous que les procédures faisant appel à l'Intelligence Artificielle seront utiles en médecine ? * *(Single choice)*

Non

↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Non'. Voyez-vous plus de risques que d'avantages à l'Intelligence Artificielle ? *** *(Single choice)*

Oui

Non

Je ne sais pas

Seulement dans les diagnostics

Seulement en traitement

En matière de diagnostic et de traitement

Connaissez-vous des directives ou des politiques en médecine qui utilisent l'Intelligence Artificielle ? * *(Single choice)*

Oui

↳ **Connaissez-vous l'une de ces directives ou politiques ? *** *(Multiple choice)*

CONSORT AI

Directives SPIRIT AI

Autre

↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Autre'. Veuillez énumérer toutes les directives ou politiques que vous connaissez*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- Aucune de ces réponses
- Non
- Non spécifié

Connaissez-vous des procédures ou des protocoles pour le partage des données médicales ? *
(Single choice)

- Oui
- ↳ **Connaissez-vous l'une de ces procédures ou protocoles ?*** (Multiple choice)

- Les principes FAIR
- Federated Learning
- Swarm Learning
- Differential privacy
- Blockchain

- Autre

↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Autre'. Veuillez énumérer toutes les procédures ou protocoles que vous connaissez*** (Text, multiple lines)

- Aucune de ces réponses
- Non
- Non spécifié

En général, dans quelle mesure pensez-vous qu'il est probable que les dossiers médicaux restent confidentiels ...

... dans la vie quotidienne à l'hôpital ? * (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

*Dans la fourchette de 1 (Je n'ai aucune confiance dans la protection des données)
à 7 (J'ai une confiance totale dans la protection des données)*

... dans les projets de recherche ? * (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Dans la fourchette de 1 (Je n'ai aucune confiance dans la protection des données) à 7 (J'ai une confiance totale dans la protection des données)

Avez-vous des enfants ? * (Single choice)

Oui

↳ **Quelle importance accordez-vous à la confidentialité des dossiers médicaux de votre enfant...**

... en pratique clinique ? * (1-7 Likert scale)

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Dans la fourchette de 1 (Je n'ai pas l'assurance que les données resteront confidentielles) à 7 (J'ai l'assurance que les données resteront confidentielles)

... dans les projets de recherche ? * (1-7 Likert scale)

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Dans la fourchette de 1 (Je n'ai pas l'assurance que les données resteront confidentielles) à 7 (J'ai l'assurance que les données resteront confidentielles)

Non

Non spécifié

Pensez-vous que la réglementation sur la protection des données de santé qui existe aujourd'hui est suffisante ? * (Single choice)

Oui

Non

↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Non'. Veuillez expliquer pourquoi*** (Text, multiple lines)

Je ne sais pas

Pensez-vous que les règles de confidentialité freinent la recherche médicale ? * *(Single choice)* Oui↳ **Vous avez répondu 'Oui'. Veuillez expliquer pourquoi*** *(Text, multiple lines)* Non Je ne sais pas

Imaginez-vous la situation suivante :

Vous êtes les parents d'un enfant à qui l'on a diagnostiqué une tumeur cérébrale inopérable (tumeur du tronc cérébral). Vous avez été informé par les oncologues pédiatriques traitants que le pronostic de la maladie est très mauvais et qu'aucune guérison n'est possible avec les thérapies conventionnelles. Comme le traitement et le pronostic de cette maladie n'ont pas fondamentalement changé au cours des 30 dernières années, on vous présente un projet de recherche dans lequel vous pouvez contribuer à développer un système d'IA qui pourrait améliorer le traitement des tumeurs du tronc cérébral.

À cette fin, toutes les données possibles de votre enfant, des symptômes aux valeurs de laboratoire, en passant par les données pathologiques, les données génétiques de la tumeur et les données d'imagerie (CT, IRM), sont nécessaires pour construire un modèle de la tumeur et trouver une option thérapeutique individuelle et nouvelle. Ces données doivent d'abord être collectées auprès de nombreux enfants atteints de la même maladie pour être traitées et évaluées dans le cadre du projet de recherche. L'espoir est que cela puisse conduire à une nouvelle option de traitement pour votre enfant.

Accepteriez-vous de fournir les données pertinentes pseudonymisées de votre enfant à des fins de recherche dans le contexte décrit ? * *(Single choice)*

Un pseudonyme est une séquence de chiffres et de lettres choisie arbitrairement. Le pseudonyme est utilisé à la place du nom réel du patient ou de son numéro de patient et sert à dissimuler son identité. Le lien entre le pseudonyme et le nom du patient est conservé dans la clinique traitante, mais n'est pas transmis. Les données sous forme pseudonyme ne peuvent donc pas être directement attribuées aux patients.

Oui

↳ Mettriez-vous les données pseudonymisées de votre enfant à la disposition de la recherche même si le pronostic était nettement meilleur ? * *(Single choice)*

Oui

Non

↳ Vous avez répondu 'Non'. Veuillez expliquer pourquoi* *(Text, multiple lines)*

Non spécifié

Non

↳ Vous avez répondu 'Non'. Veuillez expliquer pourquoi* *(Text, multiple lines)*

Non spécifié

Accepteriez-vous de faire prélever un échantillon de tissu de votre enfant pour une analyse génétique moléculaire de la tumeur et de mettre ces données à la disposition de la recherche ? Vous êtes informé que le résultat de l'analyse peut ne pas avoir de signification pour votre enfant, mais qu'il fournira en principe de nouvelles informations sur cette tumeur. Vous savez également que les données génétiques ne peuvent pas être anonymisées* *(Single choice)*

Oui

Non

↳ Vous avez répondu 'Non'. Veuillez expliquer pourquoi* *(Text, multiple lines)*

Non spécifié

Imaginez maintenant une situation différente :

Un projet de recherche sur le cancer des enfants a été couronné de succès. Un système d'IA a été développé pour le traitement des tumeurs du tronc cérébral.

Les premiers résultats de la recherche indiquent que l'utilisation du système basé sur l'IA a un meilleur pronostic que les méthodes de traitement conventionnelles. Cependant, le système doit encore être validé car le bénéfice réel doit être testé en amont.

Quelles sont selon vous les conditions requises pour participer à une telle étude avec votre enfant ? * *(Single choice)*

- Aucune
- Je dois comprendre le système informatique
- Je dois comprendre le système informatique et il doit présenter un avantage identifiable pour mon enfant
- Je vais certainement y assister car le pronostic est trop faible avec les traitements conventionnels
- Je vais certainement participer parce que je soutiens par principe la recherche
- Autre

↘ **Vous avez répondu 'Autre'. Veuillez préciser*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Avez-vous d'autres commentaires ? *(Text, multiple lines)*

Nous sommes reconnaissant de votre participation. Merci de contribuer à l'amélioration du diagnostic et du traitement des cancers chez l'enfant.

General Questionnaire on Data Protection in Childhood Cancer

German version

Willkommen!

Sehr geehrte Damen und Herren!

der Lehrstuhl von Prof. Dr. Norbert Graf von der Universität des Saarlandes führt diese Befragung durch. Für das von der EU geförderte Projekt EU4CHILD untersuchen wir, wie künstliche Intelligenz (KI) die Behandlung von krebskranken Kindern verbessern kann.

Ziel unseres Projektes ist es, Anforderungen und Notwendigkeiten für ein Ökosystem zu sammeln, in dem medizinische Daten für die Forschung zur Verfügung gestellt und mit Hilfe von künstlicher Intelligenz ausgewertet werden können. Das Ökosystem soll Ärzten helfen, die Behandlung von Kindern mit einem Tumor oder Leukämie durch KI-gestützte Software zu verbessern.

Die Umfrage ist komplett anonym. Im Rahmen dieses Fragebogens werden keine persönlichen Daten abgefragt. Bitte tragen Sie keine identifizierenden Informationen über sich selbst in die Freitextfelder ein.

Zunächst möchten wir gerne mehr über Sie erfahren und wie Sie den aktuellen Stand des Datenschutzes in der Forschung sehen...

Was ist Ihr Geburtsjahr?* *(Text, eine Zeile)*

Was ist Ihr Geschlecht?* *(Einfachwahl)*

- Männlich
- Weiblich
- Divers
- Keine Angabe

Was ist Ihr Fachgebiet oder mit welchem Hintergrund beantworten Sie diesen Fragebogen?*
(Single choice)

- Aus dem Gesundheitsbereich

↘ **Sie kommen aus dem Gesundheitsbereich. Sie sind eine... *** *(Einfachwahl)*

- Medizinische Fachkraft
- Verwaltungskraft im Gesundheitswesen (z.B. Gesundheitsministerium, Krankenhausverwaltung)
- Sonstiges

↘ **Ihre Antwort war 'Sonstiges'. Bitte nennen Sie Ihr Fachgebiet*** *(Text, Mehrere Zeilen)*

- Aus der Forschung oder IT

↘ **Sie kommen aus der Forschung oder IT. Sie sind ein-e...*** *(Einfachwahl)*

- Informatiker-in oder Modellentwickler-in
- Grundlagenforscher-in (z. B. Biologie, Genetik, Pharmazie)
- Sonstiges

↘ **Ihre Antwort war 'Sonstiges'. Bitte nennen Sie Ihr Fachgebiet*** *(Text, Mehrere Zeilen)*

- Aus einer öffentlichen Position

↘ **Sie kommen von einer öffentlichen Position. Sie sind ein-e...*** *(Einfachwahl)*

- Politische-r Entscheidungsträger-in
- Datenschutzbeauftragte-r
- Mitglied einer Patientenorganisation
- Sonstiges

↘ **Ihre Antwort war 'Sonstiges'. Bitte nennen Sie Ihr Fachgebiet*** *(Text, Mehrere Zeilen)*

- als Bürgerin oder Bürger

- Sonstiges

↘ **Ihre Antwort war 'Sonstiges'. Bitte nennen Sie Ihr Fachgebiet*** *(Text, Mehrere Zeilen)*

Ich möchte keine Angaben machen

Wie würden Sie Ihr Wissen über künstliche Intelligenz und deren Anwendung in Ihrem Fachgebiet bewerten?* (1-7 Likert Skala)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Im Bereich von 1 (sehr schlecht) bis 7 (sehr gut)

Glauben Sie, dass Verfahren, die künstliche Intelligenz verwenden, in der Medizin hilfreich sein werden?* (Einfachwahl)

- Nein
 - ↳ Ihre Antwort war 'Nein'. Sehen Sie mehr Risiken von künstlicher Intelligenz als Vorteile?*
 - (Ja/Nein)
 - Ja
 - Nein
 - Weiß nicht
- Nur in der Diagnostik
- Nur in der Behandlung
- In der Diagnostik und Behandlung

Kennen Sie Berichterstattungsleitlinien in der Medizin, welche Künstliche Intelligenz verwenden?* (Ja/Nein)

- Ja
 - ↳ **Kennen Sie eine der folgenden Berichterstattungsleitlinien?*** (Mehrfachwahl)
 - CONSORT AI
 - SPIRIT AI Richtlinien
 - Sonstiges
 - ↳ Ihre Antwort war 'Sonstiges'. Bitte listen Sie unten alle Werkzeuge auf, die Sie kennen* (Text, mehrere Linien)

- Nichts von alledem
- Nein
- Keine Angabe

Kennen Sie Verfahren oder Protokolle für den Austausch medizinischer Daten?* *(Ja/Nein)*

- Ja

↘ Kennen Sie eines der folgenden Verfahren und Protokolle?* *(Mehrfachwahl)*

- Das FAIR-Prinzip
- Federated Learning
- Swarm Learning
- Differential privacy
- Blockchain
- Sonstiges

↘ Ihre Antwort war 'Sonstiges'. Bitte listen Sie unten alle Werkzeuge auf, die Sie kennen* *(Text, mehrere Linien)*

- Nichts von alledem
- Nein
- Keine Angabe

Für wie wahrscheinlich halten Sie es im Allgemeinen, dass medizinische Unterlagen vertraulich aufbewahrt werden...

... im Klinikalltag?* *(1-7 Likert Skala)*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Im Bereich von 1 (Ich habe kein Vertrauen in den Datenschutz) bis 7 (Ich habe volles Vertrauen in den Datenschutz)

... in Forschungsprojekten?* *(1-7 Likert Skala)*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

*Im Bereich von 1 (Ich habe kein Vertrauen in den Datenschutz)
bis 7 (Ich habe volles Vertrauen in den Datenschutz)*

Haben Sie Kinder?* (Einfachwahl)

Ja

↳ Für wie wichtig halten Sie es, dass die medizinischen Unterlagen Ihres Kindes vertraulich aufbewahrt werden...

... in der klinischen Praxis?*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

*Im Bereich von 1 (Ich habe kein Vertrauen, dass die Daten vertraulich behandelt werden)
bis 7 (Ich habe volles Vertrauen, dass die Daten vertraulich behandelt werden)*

... in Forschungsprojekten?*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

*Im Bereich von 1 (Ich habe kein Vertrauen, dass die Daten vertraulich behandelt werden)
bis 7 (Ich habe volles Vertrauen, dass die Daten vertraulich behandelt werden)*

Nein

Keine Angabe

Sind Sie der Meinung, dass die heute bestehenden Regelungen zum Gesundheitsdatenschutz ausreichend sind?* (Ja/Nein)

Ja

Nein

↳ Ihre Antwort war 'Nein'. Bitte begründen Sie dies* (Text, Mehrere Zeilen)

Weiß nicht

Sind Sie der Meinung, dass die Datenschutzbestimmungen die medizinische Forschung verzögern?* (Einfachwahl)

Ja

↘ Ihre Antwort war 'Ja'. Bitte begründen Sie dies* (Text, mehrere Zeilen)

- Nein
- Weiß nicht

Stellen Sie sich vor, Sie seien in folgender Situation

Sie sind Eltern eines Kindes, bei dem ein inoperabler Hirntumor (Hirnstammtumor) diagnostiziert worden ist. Sie sind von den behandelnden Kinder-Onkologen darüber informiert worden, dass die Prognose der Erkrankung sehr schlecht ist und dass mit den herkömmlichen Therapien keine Heilung möglich ist. Da sich die Behandlung und Prognose dieser Erkrankung in den letzten 30 Jahren nicht grundlegend geändert haben, wird Ihnen ein Forschungsprojekt vorgestellt, in dem Sie helfen können, ein KI-System zu entwickeln, das die Behandlung von Hirnstammtumoren verbessern könnte.

Dazu werden alle möglichen Daten Ihres Kindes von Symptomen über Laborwerte, pathologische Daten, genetische Daten des Tumors und bildgebende Daten (CT, MRT) benötigt, um ein Modell des Tumors zu erstellen und um eine individuelle und neue Therapiemöglichkeit zu finden. Diese Daten müssen zunächst von vielen Kindern mit der gleichen Erkrankung gesammelt werden, um sie im Forschungsprojekt zu verarbeiten und auszuwerten. Die Hoffnung ist, dass dies zu einer neuen Behandlungsmöglichkeit für Ihr Kind führen kann.

Würden Sie die relevanten pseudonymisierten Daten Ihres Kindes für die Forschung im beschriebenen Zusammenhang zur Verfügung stellen?* (Ja/Nein)

Ein Pseudonym ist eine willkürlich gewählte Folge von Zahlen und Buchstaben. Das Pseudonym wird anstelle des eigentlichen Namens oder der Patientenummer von Patienten verwendet und dient zur Verschleierung der Identität. Der Zusammenhang zwischen Pseudonym und Name der Patienten ist in der behandelnden Klinik hinterlegt, wird aber nicht weitergegeben. Daten in pseudonymer Form können so nicht direkt den Patienten zugeordnet werden.

- Ja

↘ Würden Sie die relevanten pseudonymisierten Daten Ihres Kindes auch dann für die Forschung zur Verfügung stellen, wenn die Prognose deutlich besser wäre?*

- Ja

Nein

↘ Ihre Antwort war 'Nein'. Bitte begründen Sie dies* (Text, Mehrere Zeilen)

Keine Angabe

Nein

↘ Ihre Antwort war 'Nein'. Bitte begründen Sie dies* (Text, mehrere Zeilen)

Keine Angabe

Würden Sie Ihrem Kind eine Gewebeprobe zur molekulargenetischen Analyse des Tumors entnehmen lassen und diese Daten für Forschungszwecke zur Verfügung stellen? Sie sind darüber informiert, dass das Ergebnis der Analyse für Ihr Kind möglicherweise keine Bedeutung hat, aber prinzipiell neue Erkenntnisse über diesen Tumor liefern wird. Sie wissen auch, dass genetische Daten nicht anonymisiert werden können* (Ja/Nein)

Ja

Nein

↘ Ihre Antwort war 'Nein'. Bitte begründen Sie dies* (Text, mehrere Zeilen)

Keine Angabe

Stellen Sie sich nun eine andere Situation vor

Ein Projekt zur Erforschung von Kinderkrebs war erfolgreich. Es wurde ein KI-System für die Behandlung von Hirnstammtumoren entwickelt.

Erste Forschungsergebnisse deuten darauf hin, dass der Einsatz des KI-basierten Systems eine bessere Prognose hat als herkömmliche Behandlungsmethoden. Allerdings muss das System noch validiert werden, da der tatsächliche Nutzen noch weiter geprüft werden muss.

Was sind Ihre Voraussetzungen, um mit Ihrem Kind an einer solchen Studie teilzunehmen?*
(Einfachwahl)

- Keine
- Ich muss das IT-gestützte System verstehen
- Ich muss das IT-gestützte System verstehen und es sollte einen erkennbaren Nutzen für mein Kind haben
- Ich werde auf jeden Fall teilnehmen, weil die Prognose bei konventioneller Behandlung zu schlecht ist
- Ich werde auf jeden Fall teilnehmen, weil ich Forschung prinzipiell unterstütze
- Sonstiges

↘ Ihre Antwort war 'Sonstiges'. Bitte angeben* (Text, mehrere Zeilen)

Haben Sie weitere Kommentare? (Text, mehrere Zeilen)

Wir freuen uns über Ihre Teilnahme. Danke, dass Sie helfen, die Diagnose und Behandlung von Kinderkrebs zu verbessern

General Questionnaire on Data Protection in Childhood Cancer

Italian version

Benvenuto!

Gentile Signore o Signora,

Questo questionario è proposto dall'equipe del Prof. Dr. Norbert Graf dell'Università del Saarland. Nell'ambito del progetto EU4CHILD, finanziato dalla Commissione Europea, stiamo indagando su come l'Intelligenza Artificiale (AI) possa migliorare il trattamento dei bambini affetti da patologia oncologica. Lo scopo del nostro progetto è raccogliere i requisiti necessari per un ecosistema in cui i dati medici possano essere resi disponibili per la ricerca e la valutazione mediante l'Intelligenza Artificiale. L'ecosistema dovrebbe aiutare i medici a migliorare il trattamento dei bambini con malattia neoplastica, attraverso software supportati dall'Intelligenza Artificiale.

Il sondaggio è completamente anonimo. Nessun dato personale sarà chiesto come parte di questo questionario. Si prega di non inserire alcuna informazione identificativa nei campi di testo libero.

Innanzitutto, vorremmo saperne di più su di Lei e la Sua opinione riguardo allo stato attuale della protezione dei dati nella ricerca scientifica.

Qual è il Suo anno di nascita?* *(Text, single line)*

Qual è il Suo sesso?* *(Single choice)*

- Maschio
- Femmina
- Altro
- Non voglio rispondere

Qual è il Suo background in merito a questo questionario?* *(Single choice)*

- Settore sanitario

↘ **Ha scelto 'Settore sanitario'. Lei è...*** *(Single choice)*

- Un professionista sanitario
- Un altro impiegato nella Sanità (es. Ministero della Salute, personale amministrativo ospedaliero)
- Altro

↘ **Ha scelto 'Altro'. Prego specificare*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Ricerca o Data Science

↘ **Ha scelto 'Ricerca o Data Science'. Lei è...*** *(Single choice)*

- Un Data Scientist
- Un ricercatore in scienze di base (es. biologia, chimica, farmacia)
- Altro

↘ **Ha scelto 'Altro'. Prego specificare*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Posizione Pubblica

↘ **Ha scelto 'Posizione Pubblica'. Lei è...*** *(Single choice)*

- Un rappresentante politico
- Un Policy Enforcer (es. responsabile della protezione dei dati)
- Un membro di un'organizzazione di pazienti
- Altro

↘ **Ha scelto 'Altro'. Prego specificare*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Cittadino

Altro

↘ **Ha scelto 'Altro'. Prego specificare*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- Non voglio fornire informazioni al riguardo

Come valterebbe il Suo grado di conoscenza riguardo l'Intelligenza Artificiale e le sue applicazioni nella Sua area di competenza?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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In un range da 1 (molto scarsa) a 7 (ottima)

Crede che strumenti o modelli che utilizzino l'Intelligenza Artificiale potranno essere utili in medicina?* (Single choice)

- No
- ↘ Ha scelto 'No'. Ritieni che l'Intelligenza Artificiale possa avere più rischi che benefici?* (Single choice)
- Sì
- No
- Non so/Non voglio rispondere
- Solo nel processo diagnostico
- Solo nel processo terapeutico
- Sia nella diagnosi che nel trattamento

Conosce delle linee guida per il reporting di studi su intelligenza artificiale in medicina?* (Single choice)

- Sì
- ↘ Conosce qualcuna delle seguenti linee guida per il reporting?* (Multiple choice)
- CONSORT AI
- Linee guida SPIRIT AI
- Altro
- ↘ Ha scelto 'Altro'. Per favore, elenchi gli linee guida per il reporting che conosce qui sotto* (Text, multiple lines)

- Nessuno dei precedenti
- No

Non so/Non voglio rispondere

È a conoscenza di strumenti o protocolli di condivisione di dati medici?* (Single choice)

Sì

↳ **Conosce qualcuno dei seguenti strumenti o protocolli?*** (Multiple choice)

- I principi FAIR
- Federated Learning
- Swarm Learning
- Differential privacy
- Blockchain
- Altro

↳ **Ha scelto 'Altro'. Per favore, elenchi gli strumenti che conosce qui sotto*** (Text, multiple lines)

Nessuno dei precedenti

No

Non so/Non voglio rispondere

In generale, quanto ritiene probabile che i dati delle cartelle cliniche siano mantenuti riservate...

... nella pratica clinica quotidiana?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

In un range da 1 (Non ho per niente fiducia nella protezione dei dati) a 7 (Ho completa fiducia nella protezione dei dati)

... nei progetti di ricerca?* (1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

In un range da 1 (Non ho per niente fiducia nella protezione dei dati) a 7 (Ho completa fiducia nella protezione dei dati)

Ha figli?* *(Single choice)*
 Sì

↳ Quanto considera importante che i dati delle cartelle cliniche di Suo figlio siano mantenuti riservate...

... nella pratica clinica?*

(1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

*In un range da 1 (Non ho fiducia che i dati saranno mantenuti confidenziali)
a 7 (Ho piena fiducia che i dati saranno mantenuti confidenziali)*

... nei progetti di ricerca?*

(1-7 Likert scale)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

*In un range da 1 (Non ho fiducia che i dati saranno mantenuti confidenziali)
a 7 (Ho piena fiducia che i dati saranno mantenuti confidenziali)*

 No

 Non voglio rispondere

Ritiene che al giorno d'oggi la regolamentazione riguardo la protezione dei dati medici sia adeguata?* *(Single choice)*
 Sì

 No

↳ Ha scelto 'No'. Prego, spiegare il motivo * *(Text, multiple lines)*

 Non so/Non voglio rispondere

Crede che le normative sulla privacy stiano rallentando la ricerca in medicina?* *(Single choice)*
 Sì

↳ Ha scelto 'Sì'. Prego, spiegare il motivo* *(Text, multiple lines)*

- No
- Non so/non voglio rispondere

Immagini che stia vivendo la seguente situazione

Lei è il genitore di un bambino a cui è stato diagnosticato un tumore cerebrale inoperabile (tumore del tronco cerebrale). È stato informato dagli oncologi pediatri curanti che la prognosi della malattia è infausta e che al momento non esiste possibilità di cura con le terapie convenzionali. Poiché il trattamento e la prognosi di questa malattia non sono cambiati sostanzialmente negli ultimi 30 anni, Le viene proposto un progetto di ricerca in cui lei può aiutare a sviluppare un sistema di intelligenza artificiale che potrebbe migliorare il trattamento dei tumori del tronco cerebrale.

Per questo, sono necessari tutti i dati clinici del Suo bambino (sintomi, valori di laboratorio, dati patologici, dati genetici del tumore, dati di imaging come TC o RM) per creare un modello del tumore, al fine di trovare opzioni terapeutiche nuove e individualizzate. Questi dati devono essere prima raccolti da molti bambini con la stessa malattia al fine di elaborarli e valutarli nel progetto di ricerca. La speranza è che questo possa portare a una nuova opzione terapeutica per suo figlio.

Nel contesto descritto, Lei fornirebbe i dati (opportunamente resi attraverso uno pseudonimo) di Suo figlio che possano essere utili per la ricerca?* *(Single choice)*

Uno pseudonimo è una sequenza di numeri e lettere scelta arbitrariamente. Lo pseudonimo è usato al posto del nome reale del paziente o del suo numero e serve a nascondere l'identità. Il collegamento tra lo pseudonimo e il nome del paziente viene memorizzato nella clinica curante, ma non viene trasmesso. I dati in forma pseudonima non possono quindi essere assegnati direttamente ai pazienti.

- Sì

↳ **Nel caso la prognosi della malattia sia significativamente migliore rispetto allo scenario precedente, Lei fornirebbe lo stesso i dati (opportunamente resi attraverso uno pseudonimo) di Suo figlio che possano essere utili per la ricerca?*** *(Single choice)*

- Sì
- No

↳ **Ha scelto 'No'. Prego, spiegare il motivo*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

- Non voglio rispondere

No

↳ **Ha scelto 'No'. Prego, spiegare il motivo*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Non voglio rispondere

Acconsentirebbe al prelievo di un campione di tessuto da Suo figlio per l'analisi genetica molecolare del tumore e al rendere disponibili questi dati per scopi di ricerca? Lei è stato informato che il risultato delle analisi potrebbe non essere significativo per suo figlio, ma in linea di principio fornirà nuove informazioni su questo tumore. Sa anche che i dati genetici non possono essere resi anonimi* *(Single choice)*

Sì

No

↳ **Ha scelto 'No'. Prego, spiegare il motivo*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Non voglio rispondere

Ora immagina quest'altra situazione

Un progetto di ricerca in oncologia pediatrica ha avuto successo. È stato sviluppato un sistema di intelligenza artificiale per il trattamento dei tumori del tronco cerebrale.

I risultati della ricerca iniziale indicano che l'uso del sistema basato sull'intelligenza artificiale garantisce una prognosi migliore rispetto ai metodi di trattamento convenzionali. Tuttavia, il sistema deve ancora essere validato, poiché l'effettivo beneficio deve essere ulteriormente valutato.

Quali condizioni Lei pone per partecipare con Suo figlio a uno studio simile?* *(Single choice)*

Nessuna

Ho necessità di comprendere il funzionamento del sistema supportato dalla IA

- Ho necessità di comprendere il funzionamento del sistema supportato dalla IA e quest'ultimo dovrebbe apportare un visibile beneficio per mio figlio
- Parteciperò sicuramente dal momento che la prognosi con i trattamenti convenzionali è troppo sfavorevole
- Parteciperò sicuramente dal momento che in linea di principio supporto la ricerca
- Altro

↘ **Ha scelto 'Altro'. Prego specificare*** *(Text, multiple lines)*

Ha altri commenti? *(Text, multiple lines)*

Apprezziamo la Sua partecipazione, grazie mille per aver contribuito a una migliore diagnosi e/o trattamento dei tumori pediatrici!

